

D5.3

Final report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk

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D5.3/Final report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk

Led by Risklayer

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Abstract

Deliverable 5.3 of the MYRIAD-EU project, a final report, addresses the development of methods for European-hazard and multi-risk scenarios. The main objective of this deliverable is to integrate and enhance existing methodologies for assessing various natural and human-made hazards for use within the MYRIAD-EU framework.

This report details the development of methodologies for assessing multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios across Europe. It emphasises the integration of existing approaches to enhance risk quantification, focusing on creating comprehensive exposure metrics for various hazards like earthquakes, floods, volcanos and biological threats. The report discusses the extension of hazard data into multi-hazard frameworks, development of vulnerability data for direct and indirect scenarios, and evaluates different modelling approaches such as agent-based models and dynamic adaptive policy pathways. It concludes with the proposed integration of these methodologies into the MYRIAD-EU framework, setting the stage for implementing robust risk management strategies across Europe. We have integrated and enhanced existing methodologies to assess a variety of natural and human-made hazards, with a special focus on addressing multi-sector risks at the European level. Key components developed include sophisticated exposure metrics across vital sectors such as agriculture, tourism, infrastructure and socio-economic aspects.

The complexity of creating plausible temporal sequences for hazard interactions and accurately assigning return periods to these events adds a significant layer of complexity to our models. Moreover, the dynamic nature of these hazards introduces substantial uncertainty, particularly when modelling damaging events such as volcanic eruptions. Establishing impact-relevant thresholds and predicting future changes in vulnerability further complicate the assessments, as does obtaining precise data for exposure analysis, such as time-of-day data for tourist movements.

In addressing these challenges, we have employed robust methodologies for both direct and indirect risk scenarios, including agent-based models, dynamic adaptive policy pathways, and computational general equilibrium models. These methods have been critically evaluated to offer a comprehensive view of the modelling landscape, supplemented by empirical and machine learning methods to enhance the simulation of risk scenarios.

This work has practical applications, extending beyond theory for European disaster risk management initiatives. The integration of comprehensive multi-hazard and multi-risk assessments promises to enhance the resilience of European communities against a wide array of risks, fostering a proactive approach to disaster risk management and planning. However, quantifying the effectiveness of Disaster Risk Reduction measures remains challenging due to policy shifts and complex interactions between sectors and hazards. The report emphasises the reliance on high-quality data for exposure, hazard, and vulnerability from various sources, underlining the need for datasets that are tailored to the diverse sectors involved in MYRIAD-EU. These datasets must be adaptable to changing conditions and detailed enough to capture the dynamics of multi-hazard risks for both current and future scenarios.

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Abbreviations

AAL:	Average Annual Loss
ABM:	Agent-based model
A21:	NACE Rev. 2 industry sectoral classification for 21 industry groups
AHEAD:	European Archive of Historical Earthquake Data
AHP:	Analytical hierarchy process
BF:	Bushfire/Wildfire
BGS:	British Geological Survey
BN-FLEMO:	Bayesian Network-based Flood Loss Estimation Model
CIESIN:	Center for International Earth Science Information Network
CMIP5:	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5
CMIP6:	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
C3S:	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CGE:	Computable General Equilibrium
CIT:	Climate Index for Tourism
COP28:	2023 United Nations Climate Change Conference
CSF:	Critical success factor
CY:	Cyclone
DAPP:	Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways
DAPP-MR:	Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi-Risk
DFO:	Dartmouth Flood Observatory
DLR:	German Aerospace Center (<i>Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt</i>)
DMC:	Destination Management Company
DR:	Drought
DRM:	Disaster risk management
DRMKC:	Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre
EC:	European Commission
ECMWF:	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EFFIS:	European Forest Fire Information System
EGU:	European Geosciences Union
ELSUS:	European Landslide Susceptibility Map
EO4MULTIHA:	Earth Observation for high-impact multi-hazards
EPICA:	European Preinstrumental Earthquake Catalogue
EQ:	Earthquake
ERA5:	ECMWF Reanalysis v5
EU:	European Union
Eurostat:	European Statistical Office
FIGARO:	Full International and Global Accounts for Research in input-Output analysis
FL:	Flood
GDP:	Gross domestic product
GEM:	Global Earthquake Model
GFCF:	Gross fixed capital formation
GFZ:	German Research Centre for Geosciences (<i>Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum</i>)
GHSL:	Global Human Settlement Layer
GLC:	Global Landslide Catalog
GlobFire:	Global dataset of individual fire perimeters
GLOFRIS:	Global Flood Risk Image Scenarios
GPW:	Gridded Population of the World
GRACE:	Global Responses to Anthropogenic Changes in the Environment
GTAP:	Global Trade Analysis Project
H:	Historic
HANZE:	Historical Analysis of Natural Hazards in Europe
HCI:	Holiday Climate Index
HL:	Hail

HOTREC:	Confederation of National Associations of Hotels, Restaurants, Cafés and Similar Establishments in the European Union and European Economic Area
HRSL:	High Resolution Settlement Layer
HW:	Heatwave
I/O:	Input-output economic model
IIASA:	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
IPCC:	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRS:	Integrated Resilience Score
ITB:	International Tourism Conference
JRC:	Joint Research Centre
KIT:	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
LaMEVE:	Global database on large magnitude explosive volcanic eruptions
LAU:	Local Administrative Unit
MacroMIP:	https://gitlab.rz.uni-hamburg.de/BAJ2533/MacroMIP
MATRIX:	New Multi-Hazard and Multi-Risk Assessment Method for Europe
MIRACA:	Multi-hazard Infrastructure Risk Assessment for Climate Adaptation
MOU:	Memorandum of Understanding
MRIA:	Multiregional Impact Assessment Model
MVT:	Medical Value Travel
MYRIAD-EU:	Multi-hazard and systemic framework for enhancing risk-Informed management and decision-making in the EU
MYRIAD-HES:	MYRIAD – Hazard Event Sets
MYRIAD-HESA:	MYRIAD – Hazard Event Sets Algorithm
NACE:	European Classification of Economic Activities (<i>Nomenclature générale des Activités économiques dans les Communautés Européennes</i>)
NARSIS:	New Approach to Reactor Safety Improvements
NASA:	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NEX:	NASA Earth Exchange
NEX-GDDP:	NASA Earth Exchange Global Daily Downscaled Projections
NUTS:	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OFDA:	Office of Foreign Disaster Assistance
P:	Probabilistic
PARATUS:	Promoting disaster preparedness and resilience by co-developing stakeholder support tools for managing the systemic risk of compounding disasters
PC:	Performance criteria
PIK:	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
PML:	Probable Maximum Loss
PRIMAVERA:	Process-based climate simulation: Advances in high-resolution modelling and European climate risk assessments
RAIN:	Risk analysis of infrastructure networks in response to extreme weather
RCP:	Representative Concentration Pathways
RF:	Riverine flood
Risk KAN:	Risk Knowledge-Action Network
RP:	Return period
S:	Stochastic
SAM:	Social Accounting Matrix (model describing the supply and demand system in an economy)
SERA:	Seismology and Earthquake Engineering Research Infrastructure Alliance for Europe
SS:	Storm Surge
SSP:	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
TO:	Tornado
TS:	Tsunami
TSUMAPS:	Probabilistic Tsunami Hazard Maps
TsuPy:	Simulation framework to quickly compute tsunami events on a personal computer

ULL: University of La Laguna
USGS: United States Geological Survey
VO: Volcano
WCRP: World Climate Research Program
WISC: Windstorm Information Service
WP: Work Package
WRI: World Resources Institute
WS: Winter storm
WSF: World Settlement Footprint

1 Purpose of the Deliverable and Introduction

1.1 Objective

This deliverable aims to refine and expand methodologies for quantifying direct and indirect risks across multi-risk and multi-sector scenarios. Specifically, the deliverable focuses on the development and application of advanced risk models tailored to critical European sectors as outlined in Tasks 5.2 and 5.3 of the grant agreement, reproduced in part below:

- Task 5.2: Quantifying direct risk in a multi-risk and multi-sector setting - Improving methods for quantifying direct risk in a multi-risk and multi-sector setting, by: (1) extending an existing risk model to include further impacts relevant to the key sectors of MYRIAD-EU; and (2) including dynamics and feedbacks between risk drivers based on the empirical evidence generated in WP4 and within the systems at play. This is shown at an EU scale as well as for providing examples for the Danube and Canary Islands Pilots.
- Task 5.3: Quantifying indirect and interregional risk in a multi-risk and multi-sector setting - A suite of existing macroeconomic loss models (e.g. GRACE, IIASA-ABM, GTAP, MRIA) was used to analyse indirect risk and cross-sectoral dependencies of multi-hazard events from Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 with a detailed example across the EU Danube shown as part of this deliverable.

This report addresses the complex nature of multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios in Europe. It synthesises the efforts made in Tasks 5.2 and 5.3 to develop comprehensive models that capture direct and indirect risks influenced by natural and human-made hazards. The deliverable builds on the work completed in earlier tasks, which provided an understanding of the risk components—hazard, exposure, and vulnerability—and their interactions within the European scale and pilot regions.

The main objective is to integrate risk factors and mechanisms that have been empirically validated in previous work phases, enhancing the precision and applicability of risk assessments across diverse European contexts, but also to ensure that these are applicable to the sectors and stakeholders with whom we are interacting. A quantitative, semi-quantitative and qualitative modelling system interacting with indirect and macroeconomic modelling such as IIASA-ABM is wanted.

The deliverable leverages a suite of existing macroeconomic models and new modelling methods to analyse risk scenarios that extend beyond traditional single-sector assessments. This approach allows for a nuanced exploration of interregional and cross-sectoral dependencies, crucial for crafting informed, strategic responses to potential crises. The deliverable outlines the methodologies employed for risk assessment under current and projected future conditions, creating methods to utilise CMIP6 emissions and socioeconomic pathways to forecast the implications for the key sectors.

Overall, this document serves as a comprehensive guide for stakeholders involved in disaster risk management, outlining tools and insights necessary for developing robust risk mitigation strategies tailored to the needs of the European Union's member states and associated regions, including the Pilot regions. Through detailed scenario analysis and the integration of sector-specific risk metrics, this deliverable aims to enhance the resilience of European societies against the increasing frequency and complexity of multi-hazard risks.

1.2 Existing Work within MYRIAD-EU which interacts with WP5

WP1 (Diagnosis and State-of-the-Art): WP1 provides foundational data and insights that inform the methodologies used in WP5 to develop realistic multi-hazard scenarios. This includes a clear understanding of current data availability and relevant research findings. The Disaster Risk Gateway is a particularly useful resource for stakeholders to refer to in order to better understand the terminology, methods and tools employed in WP5.

WP2 (Framework and Guidance Protocols): The methodologies and frameworks developed in WP2 guide the approaches used in WP5 for creating hazard event sets and quantifying risks. This ensures that WP5 follows consistent methods aligned with project-wide ambitions. Chapter 5 illustrates how the methodology developed in WP5 is aligned with the steps of the framework developed in WP2, which includes system definition, characterisation of direct risk, characterisation of indirect risk, evaluation of direct and indirect risk, and accounting for future system state.

WP3 (Pilot Studies and Stakeholder Engagement): WP5's tool development is directly influenced by feedback from pilot studies and stakeholder engagement coordinated through WP3. This ensures that WP5's outputs are practically relevant and tailored to real-world needs. The methods employed in WP5 have been presented to stakeholders through online webinars. More of these are planned to collect feedback on the outcomes of multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios, including quantitative and semi-quantitative results, their relevance to stakeholders and potential application and next steps.

WP4 (Risk Drivers and Dynamic Feedbacks): The multi-hazard events database supports WP5 by providing a catalogue of past disasters, including information on direct impacts and risk management performance. This serves as a valuable reference for developing new risk scenarios and improving existing models. WP5 incorporates dynamic feedbacks and risk drivers identified in WP4 into its risk quantification models. Understanding how different hazards interact, and the dynamics between risk drivers, helps enhance the accuracy and relevance of risk assessments performed in WP5. The *VulneraCity* database created in WP4 aids WP5 by offering detailed information on urban vulnerability drivers for various hazards and supports the identification of broader vulnerability aspects, thereby facilitating more informed risk assessment.

WP6 (Disaster Risk Management Pathways Framework): Findings and risk scenarios from WP5 are utilised in WP6 to identify critical events and integrate them into disaster risk management strategies for specific pilot regions. The elaboration of the MYRIAD-EU Framework and the Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi-Risk (DAPP-MR) guide the formulation of Multi-Risk Pathways, which are integral for addressing long-term disaster risk reduction challenges and enhancing WP5's ability to develop adaptable, forward-looking risk scenarios. The development of a storyline approach provides a qualitative method to explore past and potential future multi-risk events, supporting WP5's efforts in visualising and implementing effective risk analyses and management strategies.

2 Main Scientific Developments

2.1 European Scale Combinations of Hazards and Exposure (Exposure-at-risk)

2.1.1 Introduction

The overlapping probability of different hazard processes defines the multi-hazard nature of any site, region or process. Key to doing this, is knowing how the hazards interact with the natural, built and human environment. Many hazards have been identified during MYRIAD-EU, and there is the need to bring this information into the hands of decision makers in a simple way to understand how often or to what magnitude they may be impacted by a particular hazard combination. To this end, an exposure-at-risk mapping is carried out for Europe with respect to multi-hazard, allowing for the examination of the probability of overlapping events temporally and spatially; for particular exposure and hazard thresholds of the different hazard event sets and outputs.

2.1.2 Historical, Stochastic and Probabilistic Hazard Footprints and Locations

The following hazards have been identified and used as part of the modelling process within WP5. Historic, Stochastic and Probabilistic methodologies are used depending on the hazard type and the methods available. An effort has been made to reduce the number of sets as part of the work in accordance with the need to provide stakeholder solutions and meaningful scenarios.

Figure 1: Integration of quantitative, semi-quantitative and qualitative approaches.

There are a variety of hazards that affect Europe with a very heterogeneous distribution of their anticipated impact. A first collection of those hazards has been compiled to harmonise their diverse raw data for being able to quantify the exposure-at-risk through multi-hazard event occurrences. To assess the probability of exposure-at-risk, a considered hazard needs to be quantified in regards of its actual impact, preferably with a spatial footprint, as well as with discrete probability of occurrence.

Hazards can be quantified under 3 different perspectives: historic, stochastic and probabilistic. Their respective definitions and available datasets are shown in Table 1. Historic events have been compiled both for earthquakes and floods. Historic earthquake events cover both 20th and 21st

century events derived from USGS and relevant pre-1904 events for each affected European country derived from the AHEAD and EPICA databases and with reconstructed event footprints based on macroseismic data points.

Stochastic datasets have been built for earthquakes based on the latest European seismic hazard model developed by the Seismological and Engineering Research Alliance for Europe (SERA) in 2020 (www.sera-eu.org). Stochastic footprints for flood are based on the work of Paprotny et al. (2024). Stochastic tornado datasets for Europe have been compiled from using a stochastic tornado model based on path characteristics via historic events; and fitting to rates of tornado activity in a larger grid cell. Winter storm events have been quantified using the PRIMAVERA European winter storm dataset (Lockwood et al. 2022). Here, event sets have been compiled from a total of 19 different climate models.

A variety of probabilistic models have been collected to cover earthquake, flood, hail, tornado and winter storms. For earthquake, tornado and winter storm, those are the same as used for the stochastic models. However, except for the compilation of individual event footprints, return periods of impact metrics were the focus. For flood, high resolution return period rasters for coastal, riverine and compound flood events have been collected using data from JRC (2024). Return periods of hail events are based on the KIT model (Kunz et al. 2019) and RAIN consortium model (2017).

This collection can be extended using the datasets detailed in the interim deliverable with the raw datasets. However, each dataset needs to be harmonised before being capable of being processed within a multi-hazard assessment framework (see Section 2.1.4). Harmonisation demands a comparable spatial aggregation between different hazards, as well as definitions on return periods or occurrence probabilities as detailed below for the case of a flood-earthquake overlap.

Table 1: Definitions of probabilistic, stochastic and historic event sets and the current availability of assessment models per peril.

Group	Description	Hazards* and Thresholds
Probabilistic	Probabilistic models capture impact occurrence probabilities derived from long-term historic observations as well as numerical and analytical assessments.	Earthquake Flood Hail Tornado Winter storm Wildfire Drought
Stochastic	Stochastic event data provides capture the occurrence probabilities of events and their respective impacts. Each event is usually modelled individually with its own unique footprint.	Earthquake Flood Tornado Winter storm
Historic	Historic events are discrete footprints of events that have already occurred. Impact metrics are calculated based on observations. The probability of occurrence is usually inferred from a complementary stochastic dataset.	Earthquake Flood Volcano (non-RP)

*Currently available and harmonised hazards. This will also be extended to also cover storm surge, landslides, wildfire or tsunami, depending on use case.

A practical example of a combination set is shown below for a Tornado-Flood combination.

1. Select location and look-ahead in time between 2 events desired for exposure at risk: (i.e. Veneto) and 60 days.
2. Define event 1 & 2: type and threshold
3. Retrieve events from the relevant single-hazard catalogues

4. Retrieve relevant administrative zones and socioeconomic information pertaining to the exposure.
5. Compute exposure-at-risk probabilities for each affected NUTS zone on the basis of the discussed methodology using the RPs (return periods) on the basis of the zonal probabilities. This can use a maximum or averaged approach depending on use case.
6. Within the WP5 software, these results will then be saved as a geopackage (with associated metadata) for use within quantitative, semi-quantitative or qualitative risk analysis/scenario management processes as needed.

Figure 2: Concurrent Tornado and Flood scenario in Veneto near Venice. This is built from a stochastic tornado set characterising single events from the stochastic set scenarios; and a flood archive by Paprotny et al., characterizing 71 years of historic and potential flood footprints.

2.1.3 Capital Stock and other Exposure Sets

The capital stock of a country is the associated fixed assets within a country. Some estimates of capital stock exist on a country level from Ministries of Finance and through other entities, however this is often not subnational except in a few cases at larger administrative zones.

The distribution at NUTS3 level allows for interactions with macroeconomic models in addition to being high enough resolution for meaningful interactions with hazards. A first step was made by

Paprotny et al. (2023) in creating a 6-sector capital stock model using fixed asset data. Adjustments have been made using subnational and national indicators in order to produce an A21 capital stock model. This allows for viewing of the sectoral assets assessed in comparison to the entire capital stock, allowing for the calculation of damage being a first major step to sectoral damage and losses in a multi-hazard environment.

A series of other parameters are presented at 3-arc second resolution, in order to correlate to hazard parameters if needed. At a NUTS-3 level, the indicators are also calculated and aggregated as part of the EU indicators set used as part of the semi-quantitative index.

Table 2: List of MYRIAD-EU sector EU-scale exposure metrics used as part of the exposure-at-risk multi-hazard interactions.

Sector	Exposure Metrics used
Finance	A21 (all economic sector capital stock), GDP
Infrastructure and Energy	Infrastructure Density
Agriculture and Food Security	Agricultural GDP, Land Use
Tourism	Tourism Expenditure, Tourism GDP, Nights Spent and MVT indicator sets distributed.
Ecosystems	Land Use
Cross-Sector	A21 Capital Stock, Population

Sector C: Manufacturing

Sector L: Real Estate Activities

Figure 3: Production of capital stock sets as well as other exposure metrics directly for the sectoral exposure at risk calculations on a NUTS3 level. Left: Sector C (Manufacturing) capital stock per NUTS3; Right: Sector L (Real Estate) capital stock per NUTS3.

One example is for tourism expenditure, for which we used the hexagons from the following paper: Combining Conventional Statistics and Big Data to Map Global Tourism Destinations Before COVID-19 (<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/00472875211051418#supplementary-materials>). In the paper they divided the world into Icosahedral Snyder Equal Area Aperture 3 Hexagonal Grid with scale factor 8, which resulted in 65,612 units with an area of 7,774 km² each. They disaggregated the sums of tourism expenditure into parts of hexagons assuming that the international and domestic tourism expenditures are proportional to the numbers of international and domestic tourists, respectively. The effect of this step was stored in the subhex.shp file. We used GHS_BUILT_V_E2025_GLOBE_R2023A_4326_3ss_V1_0 with a resolution of 3 arcsec (1/1200°) to calculate zonal statistics with the subhex.shp and to finally distribute the tourism

expenditure (Domestic and inbound) over the 3 arcsec raster grid. We then used these raster files for the calculation of inbound and domestic expenditure on NUTS3 level.

Figure 4: Distributed 3-arc-sec Inbound Tourism Expenditure for Europe for combination with exposure-at-risk calculations on a NUT3 level.

Figure 5: Distributed 3-arc-sec tourism nights spent for Europe for combination with exposure-at-risk calculations on a NUT3 level.

Figure 6: A detailed view of tourism nights spent for the main islands in the Canary Islands in Spain. Further disaggregation methods can be used.

Figure 7: Employment (number of people per pixel) in each 3 arc sec pixel for sectors G (Wholesale and retail trade), H (transportation and storage) and I (accommodation and food service facilities) distributed from NUTS3 data.

2.1.4 Stochastic and Probabilistic Exposure-at-risk

A view of a single hazard overlap for earthquake with population over a certain hazard threshold has the following form for the exposure-at-risk calculation on the basis of the above methods.

Figure 8: Exposure-at-risk for a single hazard type: Population in a 475-year RP earthquake zone where the population is situated in a hazard threshold over 0.1g.

To quantify the exposure-at-risk in a multi-risk scenario, the occurrence and impact probabilities of at least 2 different events need to be considered. Those events can be dependent or independent from each other. However, dependent-relationships can be manifold, complex and often difficult to quantify in terms of their probabilistic nature, a look at independent scenarios is preferred and more robust in terms of the underlying modelling assumptions.

As described in Section 2.1.2, various hazards have been assessed. They are either given as a discrete probability of exceedance at a certain location or as a discrete spatial footprint of an event. The footprint allows to spatially assess the impact not only at the site of interest but also in the surrounding areas. In any case, the multi-risk assessment demands an occurrence probability or probability of exceedance to start with. For a second event, which is defined similarly to the first one, a time window t in days of co-occurrence is needed. In addition, if the second event is dependent on the first one, a probability condition P_c is also needed. If both events are linearly independent, $P_c = 1$ can be assumed. Combining the individual occurrence probabilities of both events, the probability of occurrence of this scenario combination can be defined as follows:

$$P_{Occurrence} = P_{Event\ 1} \times P_{Event\ 2} \times \frac{t}{365\ days} \times P_c(P_{Event\ 1}, P_{Event\ 2})$$

If a place is affected by one of these events, the question arises whether there is exposure-at-risk. This question can be answered by introducing exceedance thresholds for each hazard above which it can be assumed that exposure is at risk. Such thresholds can be derived from vulnerability assessments, which identify above what level hazard intensity direct or indirect losses can be expected. This check can be performed independently for both events. Optionally, the threshold for the second event could be adjusted by increasing or decreasing it depending on whether the first event increased or lowered the threshold at which risk can occur. As a starting point, no event interaction is assumed. Thus, thresholds for are always the same independent of the assessed event. However, thresholds can differ between sectors, as tourist infrastructure may have a higher susceptibility of risk than for example the energy sector.

Figure 9: (top left): color-coded impact of a potential earthquake located in Romania. (top right): color-coded impact of a potential winter storm. (bottom): combination of both events, with left and right diagonal lines indicating where there is potential for exposure-at-risk for earthquake and winterstorm respectively and color-coded probability ranges from minor (25-50%) to high (>75%) probability of exposure-at-risk.

Simplified Approach:

To spatially aggregate the impacts, NUTS3 zones can be considered. For simplification, the maximum impact for each event in each zone is taken into account. In case a spatial disaggregation is available, sectoral impacts can be computed on a much higher resolution if needed.

At each location affected, e.g. a NUTS3 zone, the probability of exposure-at-risk is calculated by comparing the actual impact with the respective threshold of the relevant sector. Assuming that such a threshold is not a piece-wise stepping function, a cumulative normal distribution can be used, with the threshold as the average and a respective standard deviation, to compute a smooth transition between places of risk and no risk. Thus, the probability of exposure-at-risk for a sector of interest $P_{risk}(s)$ can be defined as follows:

$$P_{risk}(s) = P_1(s)UP_2(s)$$

With $P_1(s)$ and $P_2(s)$ being the independent threshold probabilities for both events, which is a function of the sector of interest s . Figure 9 shows an example of such a combination with an earthquake and a winter storm leading to a combined exposure-at-risk. The exposure (e.g. disaggregated tourism expenditure; or capital stock in commercial buildings) is then counted within the zones over a certain threshold combination to give the final output for the combination.

Extended Approach:

Another approach is used beyond that of the simplified method where a weighted distribution across a zone on the basis of the hazard inputs. This is important where NUTS3 zones are large or if there is a key distribution of sectoral assets somewhere within one of the zones. The combined return periods and probabilities of each hazard, over a certain duration, can be calculated in many different ways.

- The return periods of the hazard metrics can be calculated at a certain resolution to work out how often an overlap may occur. For the below example this is done at the NUTS3 resolution, using a weighted pixel value over the zone (similarly for NUTS0 for the flood scenario). For independent events, a Poisson distribution can be used.
- The return period resolution is also extremely important, because if broader scale administrative zones are used, a very different result can occur – thus this needs to be related to the level at which we want to look at the sectors.
- Alternatively, the return period of the risk metrics can be used to look at the joint probability of the events.

The selected exposure-at-risk element then can be examined and the joint probability calculated for each zone as a duration between events. Meaningful scenarios can thus be extracted depending on the stakeholder and the hazard combination desired on a higher resolution level.

Figure 10: Overlapping return period assessment associated with a 0g threshold, for a Mw8.0 earthquake scenario near Bucharest combined with flood water depths occurring within a year of the first event. The return period of the hazard is highest for smaller ground motions further away from the source (larger RPs, smaller PGAs), indicating that the far field ground motion exceeds that

of the local sources in many cases – an important observation for planning, however it depends on the threshold. Joint probabilities are seen in the lower Figure.

2.1.5 Extended use of MYRIAD-HESA

The MYRIAD-Hazard Event Sets Algorithm (MYRIAD-HESA) has been developed in WP5 to compile unique historically-based multi-hazard event sets. MYRIAD-HESA is a fully open-access method that can create multi-hazard event sets from any hazard events that occur on varying time, space, and intensity scales (Claassen et al, 2023). MYRIAD-HESA uses information on where and when a hazard occurred by using single hazard event data. Each single hazard footprint consists of a polygon that represents the spatial extent where the hazard occurred (hereinafter referred to as event polygon). Additionally, each hazard has a starting date, an end date, and a measured intensity if applicable. A visual overview of how MYRIAD-HESA compiles multi-hazard event sets is presented in Figure 11, and the steps are further explained in the caption.

Figure 11: Example of how MYRIAD-HESA operates. This figure shows both hazard pairs and hazard groups. (a) Hazards are a hazard group if all hazards overlap with each other in space and time as a pair. Here, there are two hazard groups, which are referred to as Events. Event 1 is encompassed by the black solid line, while Event 2 is encompassed by the black dashed line. Event 1 consists of three hazard pairs between Hazard 1, 2, and 3. Event 2 consists of one hazard pair between Hazard 3 and 4. (b) A dynamic hazard has to overlap with the other hazards during at least one of the overlapping time-steps. Here, Hazard 1 is a dynamic hazard. Therefore, its event polygon can change over time. Hazard 2 and Hazard 3 are not dynamic hazards. Their polygons remain the same between their start time and end time.

We have exemplified our approach by compiling a global multi-hazard event set database, spanning from 2004 to 2017, which includes eleven hazards from varying hazard classes (e.g. meteorological, geophysical, hydrological and climatological). This global database provides new scientific insights on the frequency of different multi-hazard events and their hotspots as showcased in Figure 12.

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intensity scales (Claassen et al, 2023). MYRIAD-HESA uses information on where and when a hazard occurred by using single hazard event data. Each single hazard footprint consists of a polygon that represents the spatial extent where the hazard occurred (hereinafter referred to as event polygon). Additionally, each hazard has a starting date, an end date, and a measured intensity if applicable.

Alongside MYRIAD-HESA, the multi-hazard event sets, MYRIAD-HES, is openly available to further increase the understanding of multi-hazard events in the disaster risk community. The open-source nature of MYRIAD-HES(A) provides flexibility to conduct various multi-risk assessments. For example, MYRIAD-HES is used in MYRIAD-EU's WP4 to study multi-hazard susceptibility and investigate multi-hazard recovery with the use of nighttime lights to define economic exposure as a function in time. Additionally, MYRIAD-HESA can be used with higher resolution data in an area of interest. For example, MYRIAD-HESA has been adapted to provide multi-hazard spatio-temporal dynamic footprints for present and future risk scenarios under different climate change projections in the Veneto Pilot (WP3). MYRIAD-HESA has also been tested in MIRACA, a Horizon 2020 project on multi-hazard infrastructure assessment. Here, higher resolution data for the EU has been compiled, which will also be available open access soon.

Figure 12: The most frequent hazard pairs globally. Here, there is no distinction which hazard occurs first in the pair, for example, 'dr & hw' could be a drought followed by a heatwave as well as a heatwave followed by a drought. The acronyms for each hazard are included in the table on the right-hand-side. White areas are the ocean or a place with no hazard pairs.

2.1.6 Further Multi-Hazard and Multi-Risk sets

In addition to historical multi-hazard events, it is also crucial to be prepared for potential multi-hazard events, which may not have been observed in the past. Therefore, within MYRIAD-EU we have developed a statistical Python package, VineCopulas, that has enabled us to study multi-hazard dependencies. With the use this package, the statistical dependencies between hazards are calculated based on copulas between variables, such that we can better understand the likelihood of two extremes co-occurring at the same time. For example, it can be evaluated what the likelihood is of both extreme rainfall as well as extreme wind at the same time across Europe. Such tools enable more informed decision-making for the future to better diversify risk.

For the stochastic multi-hazard dependencies, we are conducting a study that uses wind speed, temperature and precipitation data from the ERA5-land reanalysis data set as input for the vine copula model. The vine copula model will be run in using the open-source Python package

VineCopulas that has been developed in MYRIAD-EU. For more information on vine copulas and the package we have developed, the software documentation can be addressed (Claassen et al. 2024).

2.2 Future Climate and Socioeconomic Scenarios

2.2.1 Background

Climate change significantly impacts natural hazards, environments, economies, and sectors such as tourism and agriculture, presenting unprecedented challenges. Climate change is expected to increase the frequency and intensity of multi-hazard events in the future. To conduct robust multi-risk assessments, current and future conditions should be considered, which is why the MYRIAD-EU project incorporates future climate and socioeconomic scenarios.

Future climate scenarios are based on CMIP6 (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6) data, the latest iteration of the World Climate Research Program (WCRP) global climate model (Eyring et al., 2016). CMIP6 provides common standards for comparativeness between different climate models. Unlike station data, which have high spatio-temporal resolution and accuracy, and are best for calibrating and validating climate models, CMIP6 data are crucial for understanding and projecting large-scale climate processes and atmospheric interactions on global and regional scales.

The CMIP6 climate models contain future projections based on different future scenarios, such as Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSP) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP), describing the respective model input assumptions for certain pathways of human development and decarbonisation, respectively. The different scenarios are elaborated in more detail in Appendix C. The RCPs were initially developed for the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and describe different projections of greenhouse gas emissions and atmospheric concentrations.

For CMIP6 future climate projections, the RCP and SSP scenarios are combined. This leads to the nomenclature SSPX-Y, where X and Y represent the number of the specific SSP and RCP scenario, respectively. (MFE, 2024) WP5 uses primarily the SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios for CMIP6 data in the base set (and uses some older outputs of RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios for CMIP5 data inherently through some other European sets).

The SSP2-4.5 describes an intermediate socioeconomic and emission pathway. All sectors such as infrastructure, tourism and finance are likely to keep their emissions reasonably constant out till 2050, and then slowly reduce them by transitioning towards renewable energies. As such, there would be less investment initially into clean energy and improved energy standards (and indeed food/security aspects) than in SSP1-2.6, which would achieve net zero around 2075 thus supporting ecosystems and potentially meaning more sustainable food systems. In these low and intermediate scenarios, the multiplier effects on the hazard metrics will likely be lower than in the major SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5.

The latter two scenarios assume that greenhouse gas emissions will be doubled by 2100 and 2050, respectively, from the current level, representing a high and very high emission pathway. SSP3-7.0 is based on socioeconomic fragmentation where nationalistic policies impede global cooperation, resulting in elevated greenhouse gas emissions and significant climate impacts. The energy sector is dominated by fossil fuels with very little investment into sustainable energy resources. The agrifood sector faces climate impacts like droughts, floods and extreme weather events, which are severely affecting the productivity and resulting in increased food prices and disrupted supply chains. As a result of shifting climatic conditions, traditional tourism destinations may experience a decline in visitor numbers as travel patterns change.

The more extreme SSP5-8.0 scenario assumes a continued reliance on fossil fuels driven by rapid economic growth and technological advancement, with limited efforts to mitigate emissions. Consequently, this leads to a significant rise in global temperatures and severe climate impacts. Many tourism destinations are less attractive due to extreme climatic conditions, with especially

coastal areas facing major challenges. The infrastructure sector will become much more vulnerable and substantial investments in climate-resilient infrastructure are necessary. The agrifood sector will require farmers to adopt new agricultural practices and change crop varieties to ensure they are more suitable to the new climate conditions.

Table 10 illustrates the sectors in the five focus regions of MYRIAD-EU, which are all impacted by climate change, as well as some of the dominant hazards that they are facing.

All the CMIP6 runs do not adequately address convective processes, thus increases in convective hazards such as tornado or hail should be undertaken through empirical trending.

2.2.2 Future Climate-Socioeconomic Scenarios for use in MYRIAD-EU

Future climate and socioeconomic model results are used in the WP5 event modelling. Specifically, the NEX-GDDP-CMIP6 climate dataset, produced by NASA Earth Exchange (NEX) and hosted by Microsoft Planetary Computer, is incorporated. This dataset is characterised by global, high-resolution, bias-corrected climate change projections based on SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios for the period 2015-2100. Additionally, it includes historical data for 1950-2014. The variables used to calculate the climate indices are listed in Appendix C.

A total of 33 climate indicators are calculated from these atmospheric variables, such as *heat_index*, *humidex*, and *maximum_1-day_precipitation* (rx1days), using *xarray* and *xclim* python packages. A detailed list of the indicators for MYRIAD-EU can be found in Appendix C. These climate indicators are averaged over 15 different experiments, resulting in ensemble data. Furthermore, the indicators are also temporally aggregated, with each year representing an average over a +/- 10-year window, yielding a total time window of 20 years. Some indicators are provided daily (365 data points per year), while others are annual aggregates (e.g., annual mean/sum, number of days above a threshold). Additionally, the *Climate Index for Tourism* and *Holiday Climate Index* from Copernicus (C3S, 2019) describe climate suitability for beach and urban tourism, respectively. An example of the indices is shown in Figure 13. The historic ensemble dataset is a 20-year average from 1986-2005. Future projections are provided for 2030, 2050, and 2090 based on a 20-year average as well.

Figure 13: Climate Index for Tourism (beach) and Holiday Climate Index (urban) for July 2090 with RCP4.5. It is nicely shown that during summer the Mediterranean area favours beach tourism while the Alps and Scandinavia are more suitable for urban tourism.

2.3 Vulnerability functions for use in MYRIAD-EU

2.3.1 Extracted Database

A database of vulnerability and fragility functions is needed to convert any exposure and hazard into risk. The idea of MYRIAD-EU is not to be exhaustive, but to provide as many use cases as possible in this sphere which can be of use to the stakeholders, and the Pilots within MYRIAD-EU.

To this end, a database has been set up of fragility and vulnerability functions for various purposes for use within MYRIAD-EU for particular sectors and hazards of which empirical and analytical vulnerability functions are produced.

Table 3 includes the types of functions included as part of the database for addressing the challenges studied in MYRIAD-EU. The functions are either empirical, analytical, expert-opinion/hybrid in nature.

Table 3: Vulnerability and Fragility function types added to the database for use within MYRIAD.

Sectors	Hazards	Types of functions
Financial	EQ, CY, FL, SS, BF, TO, HL, HW, VO, TS, RF, WS	Sectoral stock functions, building damage functions, fatality functions, disruption
Infrastructure + Energy	EQ, CY, FL, SS, BF, TO, HL, HW, VO, TS, RF, WS	Infrastructure damage functions, stock damages, road, electric, water connectivity
Tourism	EQ, CY, FL, SS, BF, HL, HW, VO, TS, RF, WS	Hotel/Accom damage, Tourism stock functions, beach downtime.
Social/human economy interaction	DR, EQ,	Population, employment.
Agriculture /Food Security	VO, TS, RF, HL, BF, DR, EQ	Crop Damage, Buildings
Economy	EQ, FL	Direct capital damages per sector
Ecosystems	WS, FL, DR, VO	Forestry damage

Figure 14: Median Sectoral Vulnerability functions for Eastern Europe for Earthquake. The sectors are displayed based on the NACE standard (see Table 10 Appendix B – Exposure data sets and sectors for details).

The extension to time-dependent vulnerability functions has been explained in D4.4, where a large number of functions have been reviewed. In the coming few months these can be added into the database where appropriate and recommended for use. Empirical data and functions will be included as part of deliverable 4.5 in Month 45.

Various partners are also producing additional vulnerability and fragility functions along the different sectors including a volcano database via BGS, and Canary Islands specific functions as part of the Canary Islands Case Study.

An initial compendium was started characterising all possible vulnerability and fragility functions, however, it was decided after the WP3-4-5 interactions as part of the webinars, that the vulnerability database would be more targeted along the sectors and key risk metrics and to reduce the scope to something manageable, for hazards specific to Europe. The intention is for the database to be improved and extended over the course of the project.

2.3.2 Vulnerability

VulneraCity is a comprehensive database designed to support the investigation and analysis of the drivers of urban vulnerability to a range of natural hazards, namely coastal flooding, pluvial flooding, earthquakes, heat waves, drought and waterborne diseases. This database originates from a systematic global literature review encompassing more than 3,000 articles conducted by Stolte et al (2024).

Its primary purpose is to assist researchers, urban planners and policy makers in understanding the complex and multifaceted nature of urban vulnerability. This dataset supports the understanding of how vulnerability affects the different indicators used in the semi-quantitative method, which is described in detail in Chapter 2.4.

In certain cases, *VulneraCity* can be used as a modifier for the quantitative vulnerability functions, where the building type or typology matches with one of the quantitative vulnerability functions.

2.3.3 Heatwave functions

De Polt et al. (2023) explore the impact of heatwaves on various societal metrics. The research highlights that heatwaves have increased in frequency, duration, and intensity, trends that are expected to continue due to climate change. The research focuses on heatwave durations that have significant societal impact, analysing related metrics such as health (hospitalisations and mortality rates) and public attention (Google trends, news coverage). The study finds that heatwaves lasting between two weeks and two months have the most pronounced societal impacts.

Figure 15: Heatwave dynamics for vulnerability functions.

This research is integrated to improve heatwave impact analyses as follows:

- Heatwave fatality functions: Adapting heatwave duration data has established more accurate fatality functions that can be used in risk simulations.

- Sector specific vulnerability: For sectors like healthcare and tourism integrating heatwave duration and intensity data helps model potential disruptions or increased demands.

2.4 Semi-Quantitative Index Methods

2.4.1 General

The methodology for the semi-quantitative composite index to complement the direct risk assessment methodology is based on a combination of quantitatively derived or modelled indicators (Physical Risk) and a semi-quantitative index (Impact Factor) to derive an Integrated Resilience Score (IRS). The IRS framework combines the direct physical damages with the multi-dimensional vulnerability drivers (i.e. social, economic, infrastructure and environmental factors). In this way, the IRS Quantitative Score facilitates the comparison of risk among different Local Administrative Units (LAU) (i.e. municipalities). The physical risk indicators are based on the interactions of the multi-hazard scenarios, vulnerability and exposure and used from risk model outputs (e.g. damage to buildings, connectivity loss of transportation and disruption to power network). The socio-economic fragility and the lack of resilience are a set of factors (related to indirect or intangible effects) that aggravate the physical risk (potential direct effects). Thus, the total risk depends on the direct effect, or physical risk, and the indirect effects expressed as a factor of the direct effects. Therefore, the total risk can be expressed as follows:

$$IRS_{Quant} = R_F (1 + F)$$

where R_F is the physical risk index and F is the aggravating coefficient of the impact factor ($1+F$). The physical risk, R_F , is evaluated in the same way:

$$R_F = \sum_{i=1}^p w_{RFi} \times F_{RFi}$$

where p is the total number of descriptors of physical risk index, F_{RFi} are the component factors and w_{RFi} are their weights respectively. The factors of physical risk, F_{RFi} , are calculated using the gross values of physical risk descriptors such as the number of deaths, injured or the destroyed area, and so on. It has to be mentioned that although important, the calculation of physical risk scenarios is not the main objective of an integrated risk assessment. Coefficient, F , depends on the weighted sum of a set of aggravating factors related to the socio-economic fragility, F_{FSi} , and the lack of resilience of the exposed context, F_{FRj} :

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^m w_{FSi} \times F_{FSi} + \sum_{j=1}^n w_{FRj} \times F_{FRj}$$

where w_{FSi} and w_{FRj} are the weights or influences of each i and j factors and m and n are the total number of descriptors for social fragility and lack of resilience respectively. Each of the factors used in the calculation of the IRS_{Quant} captures different aspects and is quantified in different units. Because of that, certain scaling procedures are needed to standardize the values of each descriptor and convert them into commensurable factors.

2.4.2 Tourism

The semi-quantitative index methods described above have been applied to the tourism sector, which directly and indirectly supports one in 10 jobs globally. The vulnerability of the tourism sector to various shocks and stresses has been assessed using publicly available tourism indicators to establish a tourism vulnerability index. The analysed data provides a comprehensive stocktake for the resilience of the tourism sector through indicators that track key connections between disaster risk from a multi-hazard perspective, climate change, and tourism's vulnerability to disruptions in interconnected sectors such as infrastructure, ecosystems, socio-economic and health. Over 90 metrics were identified and 40 analysed at the sub-national NUTS 2 and NUTS 3 levels, providing

a comprehensive framework to assess the tourism sector's progress in climate and disaster resilience at the sub-national level. Criteria for metric selection prioritised meaningfulness, policy relevance, scientific acceptance, reliability, upgradability, and geographical representativeness for EU-wide comparisons.

Figure 16: Indicators for the Tourism Multi-hazard vulnerability index using a base weighting across indicators.

The purpose of the tourism disaster vulnerability index is to provide a holistic measure of vulnerability specific to tourism destinations, identify concentrations of vulnerabilities and support targeted and prioritized cross-sector interventions. We therefore generate insights for tourism stakeholders at local, regional, and national levels about risk concentrations and factors driving vulnerability. The methodology assesses the risk of multiple hazards and impacts to a particular sector, allowing sector stakeholders to prioritize resilience improvement strategies.

2.4.3 Indirect Effects

Given the indicator sets collected across the EU at different NUTS levels of resolution, an adaptation of Daniell et al. (2018) can be produced to provide an additional view of indirect risks associated with a multi-hazard event. The indicators are classed into 5 key primary groups encompassing the Input and productive factors (parameters like Includes an EU adaptation of the indirect loss module.

Table 4: Indirect Vulnerability Index indicator types and groupings.

Primary Group	Indicator Types
Input and productive factors	GDP classes, GFCF, employment ratios and insurance penetration
Supply chain and cross sectoral impacts	Industrial area, clustering of sectors, demand, accessibility.
Infrastructure	Telephones, Transport volumes, Air cargo, Power consumption, water supply, self-supply of utilities and Infrastructure starts.
Social/human economy interaction	Household consumption, Staying potential, Training and innovation, Poverty/inequality, Crime Rate, Education, Community Expenditure
Impact Driven	Government effectiveness, Rule of law, Payment investment, Population distribution, Budget effects, Clean-up costs.

Indicators are selected for every grouping, and the indirect disaster vulnerability index is aimed to provide a measure of vulnerability for a particular sector or group of sectors in a certain location and help to identify where traditional indirect loss modelling (e.g. CGEs, SAMs and I/O models) is required, or also indications of potential indirect loss factors in the absence of the ability to apply the aforementioned indirect loss models. More detailed information on the models is shown in Appendix D – Modelling approaches.

2.5 Sectoral Direct and Indirect Quantitative Risk Methodologies

2.5.1 Direct Sectoral Quantitative Modelling

The sectoral direct risk methodology uses combinations of hazards interacting with the built environment or population, combined with vulnerability or fragility functions to give insight into the risk. The aforementioned hazard scenarios can be created using either a stochastic event, probabilistic value for a site or a historic event. Depending on the hazard type and temporal sequence to the next event, then the hazard metrics when independent, can simply be used in conjunction with a vulnerability function or fragility function for that hazard metric which is sector specific. For example, the process for financial capital stock for an overlapping tornado is as follows:

Hazard (location specific raster over time or maximum/mean

- Tornado: $H_1 = F_{scale}$ or *Velocity in m/s*
- Earthquake: $H_2 = Sa$ or *MMI* or some other such parameter depending on E (exposure type)

Exposure: In this case, we examine the economic value of financial assets and the Number of financial institutions, quantity of insured buildings at a grouping of locations.

$$E_{finance}$$

Vulnerability: We use vulnerability functions that relate the hazard metric to the expected damageability of the elements, $V_{finance}(H)$, is created on the basis of sector specific functions, expert judgement, analytical or empirical work. Examples of tornado include the work of Feuerstein et al. (2011), for earthquake, we can use the sector specific functions produced as part of WP5. The uncertainty is generally presented through a beta or lognormal distribution. Fragility functions could also be used if available or any form of metric.

$$DR_{finance} = V_{finance}(H) \times E_{finance}$$

We need to integrate the formula over the duration of the hazards and consider the rate of change of vulnerability and exposure over time, in order to account for dynamics of socioeconomic processes and/or hazard-related processes. This overlaps with D4.3 in terms of the functions for heatwave; and is the way that the dynamic vulnerability functions come into the analysis. This might require a more dynamic model, potentially involving differential equations to simulate the time-varying nature of the hazards and their impacts.

Let's denote:

- t_{h1}, t_{h2} : Duration of hazard types 1 and 2 over all locations
- t_{d1}, t_{d2} : Duration of damage effects from hazard types 1 and 2 over all locations
- $E(t)$: Time-varying exposure.
- $V_1(t), V_2(t)$: Time-varying vulnerability functions for hazard types 1 and 2.
- $H_1(t), H_2(t)$: Time-varying hazard intensities for hazard types 1 and 2.
- $I_{combined}(t)$: Time-varying combined impact at a location.

The combined impact $I_{combined}(t)$, considering the overlapping and sequential nature of hazards, is formulated as:

$$I_{combined}(t) = \int_0^{t_{end}} (V_1(t) \cdot E(t) \cdot H_1(t) + V_2(t) \cdot E(t) \cdot H_2(t) - \text{OverlapAdjustment}(t)) dt$$

Inherently for all locations.

The function $OverlapAdjustment(t)$ accounts for the overlapping duration of hazards and their damage effects. The actual form of this function will depend on the specific interaction between the two hazards.

The overlap adjustment function could be expressed, for example, as:

$$OverlapAdjustment(t) = \min(V_1(t) \cdot H_1(t), V_2(t) \cdot H_2(t)) \cdot E(t) \cdot O(t)$$

where $O(t)$ is a function that quantifies the extent of overlap based on the timing and duration of the hazards.

This integral represents the cumulative effect of both hazards over time, with adjustments for how exposure and vulnerability change during this period. Solving this integral requires specific functional forms for $V_1(t)$, $V_2(t)$, $E(t)$, $H_1(t)$, and $H_2(t)$, along with empirical data for validation.

Most cases are static currently in WP5, given the complexity in the direct vulnerability adjustment, with the dynamics currently extended mostly through the indirect damage module. However, the temporal difference in the hazard due to climate change can be brought in as an adjustment and this will be undertaken for a few cases in the Danube and Canary Islands.

Figure 17: Direct risk methodology schematic.

Table 5: List of MYRIAD-EU sectors and some key potential direct and indirect damage metrics identified. Not all can be directly calculated at EU scale.

Sector	Potential Direct and Indirect Damage Metrics
Finance	Investment & Built Stocks: Replacement, Reconstruction, Depreciated Cost, Reconstruction with International Laborers, Insurance Cost, Contents Included, Risk Layers
Infrastructure and Energy	Capital Stock, Useability and Damage Analysis, Network Analysis
Agriculture	Crop, Land Use, Stock Dependent, Food
Tourism	Hotels, Interactions with Sectors, Population Metrics, Socioeconomic Information, Fatality & Disruption Functions
Ecosystems and Forestry	Forest damage, Environmental metrics
Food and Agriculture	Food/Agriculture (Impact on Supply Chains and Critical Infrastructure)

2.5.2 Sectoral Indirect Quantitative Modelling

Indirect risks are evaluated using different macroeconomic models. For the quantification of indirect effects across Europe the selection of modelling approaches was narrowed down to the IASA agent-based model (ABM), now extended to the EU scale at the country level, Computational General Equilibrium models (CGE), and the Multi-Regional Impact Assessment (MRIA) model. In addition to the CGE model GRACE described in D5.2, we have begun cooperation with the modelling groups at the University of Melbourne and the University of Graz to include their respective CGE models in our efforts to describe and understand the mechanisms driving indirect effects of hazard events in macroeconomic models. Appendix D – Modelling approaches replicates a description of these modelling approaches from D5.2 (2024).

In order to compare the indirect effects across these different modelling approaches the model settings are harmonised as much as possible. The models are initialised for the common start year 2014 and are based on the same version of the underlying economic database (GTAP 2010).

The methodology for the evaluation of indirect risk is based on a four-step process. First, the model is run without any shocks from the common base year, to obtain the baseline economic developments. Second, the shock is applied to the model variables in the first time step and the model is run to determine the outcomes of the shock scenario. In the case of sequential compound event scenarios, the second shock is applied at a later time step of the model. Third, the differences between the shocked and baseline model runs are calculated. This difference contains only effects of the shock on the modelled economies. Finally, the indirect effects are disentangled from the direct effects (the shocks).

As introduced in D5.2 we investigate indirect effects in three dimensions: intersectoral, interregional, and intertemporal. These indirect effects occur when a sector, region, or time step not impacted by the shock exhibits differences to the baseline. Intersectoral and interregional indirect effects are generally a result of supply chain linkages across sectors and regions. Intertemporal indirect effects can be driven by reconstruction of damaged capital and infrastructure over time and, if the model allows for this, by persistent shifts in demand to different suppliers following the interruption of the original suppliers in the wake of the hazard event. The way in which reconstruction is modelled especially affects intertemporal indirect effects. Reconstruction can be modelled endogenously or exogenously. In the case of endogenous reconstruction, modelled economic actors invest in the damaged capital stocks to rebuild them, possibly requiring loans that will have to be repaid over time. The speed of reconstruction is then a result of the available funds of economic actors and the cost of materials. If reconstruction is modelled exogenously, this can take the form of an assumed rate of reconstruction.

The ABM is based on a model of the Austrian economy (Poledna et al., 2023) and its customised version for assessment of economic consequences of flood damages (Bachner et al., 2023). As part of the MYRIAD-EU project, the model has been extended to cover the EU countries. The model now covers 26 EU countries (except Malta), including 9 countries in the Danube Region, encompassing 237 NUTS-2 regions. It includes 64 industries based on the NACE classification. The model was calibrated using FIGARO and Eurostat data, with 2016 as the baseline year. It simulates economic activity at quarterly timesteps over a three-year horizon, resolving all economic actors (households, firms, banks, and the government) for which data are available in national accounts (Figure 18). The extension of the model has come at the loss of spatial resolution and actor density. While the original model represented each spatially explicit household and firm in the Austrian economy, the European version aggregates the spatial dimension to the country level and operates with a selection of heterogeneous actors per country and sector, intended to mimic the actual distributional properties of households and firms in these countries and sectors.

Figure 19: The $M_w8.0$ earthquake scenario used.

The $M_w8.0$ earthquake is followed a few months later by a flood scenario from the historic 70-year series. Here a 2010-like flood scenario is used where flooding occurred throughout Eastern Europe.

Figure 20: The 2010-like flood scenario used as part of the combined earthquake then flood scenario.

Vulnerability functions on an A21 level (21 sectors of the economy) were used in order to derive the direct damages associated with the hazard scenarios. These followed the methodology of Leon et al. (2022) and provide first pass vulnerability functions vs. the hazard metrics of spectral acceleration (adjusted from intensity as shown in the earthquake scenario) and water height (as shown in the flood scenario diagram).

Figure 21: Top: Mw8.0 earthquake scenario total damages by sector (Real Estate Activities). Bottom: A 2010-like flood scenario total damages by sector (Real Estate Activities).

At the time of writing, only results from the IIASA ABM and preliminary results from the GRACE CGE model are available. In order to evaluate the direct impact scenarios in each of the models, the scenario specifications have to be adjusted to match the structure of these models and in some cases adjustments to the models themselves are needed to incorporate the scenarios. These efforts are ongoing and will be continued in the coming year.

The scenarios investigated using the IIASA ABM are focused on the Danube pilot region. Hazards selected for the scenarios are an earthquake with its epicentre in Romania and a flood along the Danube river. In addition to single hazard events, consecutive hazard events (an earthquake followed a year later by a flood and a flood followed a year later by an earthquake) are also considered. All in all four scenarios were evaluated in addition to the model baseline. Even though the direct impacts are located solely within the Danube region, the impacts propagate across all countries in the model. From a modelling perspective the locations of the impacts are arbitrary, the Danube region was chosen as it is one of the pilot regions of the project.

Figure 22: Time series of the relative differences in the real economic output of each of the countries included in the model compared to the baseline scenario without any hazard event. Time steps are in quarter years.

Following the methodology described in section 2.5.2 above, Figure 22 shows the effects that the four scenarios have on the real output of the countries included in the model. The structural differences in the effects of the chosen hazards is clearly visible. The earthquake destroys a large amount of capital in the affected regions, while a flood causes smaller levels of destruction in a wider area. We analyse the single hazard earthquake scenario in more detail below.

To better understand the mechanisms of the indirect effects, we further analyse the changes in the sectoral output of the countries at different points in time. Sector definitions follow the NACE standard, see Table 10 in Appendix B for details. The ABM model resolves economic activities at the two-digit sectoral level. For this presentation of the results, we have aggregated the results to the single digit sector classification.

Sectoral output changes to the baseline in the first timestep (Figure 23) correspond to the direct impacts specified by the scenario at the time that the first hazard takes place. Damage caused by the earthquake severely reduced the output of most sectors of the Romanian economy. The only sectors initially unaffected were mining and quarrying (B), manufacturing (C), and energy supply (D). The most affected sector was accommodation and food services (I), which is a comparatively small part of the Romanian economy. The sector with the largest impact on the overall reduction in economic output was wholesale and retail trade (G). This sector was strongly affected (a reduction in output for this quarter by over 10% compared to the baseline) and makes over ten percent of the Romanian economy. The earthquake also reduced output of some sectors in the Bulgarian economy to a lesser extent. It is important to note that in this scenario the transport sector had less damage overall as compared to wholesale and retail trade proportionally. Depending on the earthquake dynamics, events may have very different ratios of damage, thus influencing the ABM results.

Figure 23: Sectoral changes in output relative to the baseline scenario for the first time step, Q1, the moment the hazard hits. Sectors are according to NACE, see the Appendix B for more information. Wedges on the inside of the circle correspond to relative decreases in output compared to the baseline, while wedges outside the circle correspond to relative increases compared to the baseline. The width of each wedge corresponds to the relative importance of the sector for the respective countries' overall output. Countries are coloured corresponding to the overall relative change in real output compared to the baseline.

Over the first four quarters after the first hazard has hit, some of the damages to the Romanian economy have been repaired (Figure 24). However, the economy is still strongly lagging behind the baseline. For the Bulgarian economy the hazard has turned into a boon for multiple sectors. While the wholesale sector (G) still lags behind the baseline scenario, other sectors more than compensate for this. Overall, the Bulgarian economy has a larger output one year after the earthquake compared to the baseline. Across the modelled countries, the construction sector (F) strongly benefits from the Romanian reconstruction efforts. The interregional indirect effects of the earthquake at this point in time appear to be positive for the countries not directly impacted by the hazard. An exception to this observation is Luxembourg, where the financial and insurance sector (K) is negatively affected. As this sector makes up a large proportion of the Luxembourgian economy, overall output of that country falls behind the baseline.

Figure 24: Sectoral changes in output relative to the baseline scenario for time step Q5, one year after the hazard hit. For a detailed description of chart element see Figure 23

In quarter 9, two years after the hazard hits, the picture changes from a general increase in economic output, benefiting from the reconstruction investments, to a general reduction in economic output relative to the baseline in Figure 25. This can be explained as an effect of the fact that reconstruction is financed through debt and that capital invested in reconstruction will lead to

a shortfall in other sectors of the economy, compared to the baseline. Across Europe, two years after the earthquake, the finance and insurance (F) and manufacturing (C) sectors fall behind the baseline scenario. Within Romania the originally unaffected mining (B), manufacturing (C), and energy supply (D) sectors are now also negatively affected.

Figure 25: Sectoral changes in output relative to the baseline scenario for time step Q9, two years after the hazard hit. For a detailed description of chart element see Figure 23.

Summarising the above along the three dimensions of indirect effects: From a sectoral perspective the construction sector (F) benefits from an earthquake hazard event, while the finance and insurance (K) and manufacturing (C) sectors experience the strongest negative effects. Other sectors experience smaller variations in their economic outputs. From the interregional perspective areas not directly affected benefit from reconstruction activities. Inter-temporally the initial benefits experienced by neighbouring countries are followed by a general reduction in economic output relative to the baseline.

Preliminary results from the CGE model GRACE indicate effects an order of magnitude smaller than those discussed above. In this model, in the countries not directly affected by the earthquake, the Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing (A), Mining and Quarrying (B), and the Transportation and Storage (H) sectors are most affected. There are no comparable benefits in the other countries resulting from the hazard events, as in the ABM. Within the affected countries, Romania and Bulgaria, almost the entire economy is affected by the hazard event. As the event itself did not affect all sectors, this is partly due to intersectoral indirect effects within these countries. An exception is the Agriculture, Forestry, and Fishing sector (A) in Romania which is reported to grow by almost two percent as a consequence of the hazard event. The preliminary results from the GRACE model do not allow investigation of intertemporal indirect effects, as the model was run in a static configuration. The

results can be understood as the consequences in the hypothetical scenario where the impact is persistent (no recovery occurs) and a new market equilibrium develops with the reduced sectoral outputs in the affected countries.

2.6.2 Semi-Quantitative Scenarios

Drawing upon the methodology outlined in section 2.4.2, and the above scenario, we linked the tourism indicators to these hazard scenarios. An analytical hierarchy process (AHP) was followed for multi-criteria decision-making to determine weights. The defined goal was to improve resilience, in this case of the tourism sector, defined as the tourism sector's ability to withstand and quickly recover from a disaster event. Within each category and indicator, pairwise comparisons were performed based on their relative importance in reaching the goal of achieving resilience. The resulting weights are shown using a numerical scale of 0 – 1, with 0 contributing the least and 1 contributing the most to withstanding and recovering from a hazard event.

How important is the indicator to the tourism sector to withstand or recover from the event?

Tier 1 (Category)	Base Weight (Category)	Tier 2 (Indicator)	Importance for Earthquake Resilience	Importance for Flood Resilience
Basic Tourism Descriptors	0.1724	Basic Data	0.0345	0.0345
		Tourism Capacity	0.1379	0.1379
Tourist Risks	0.2069	Safety & Security	0.2069	0.2069
Socio-economic (Tourism)	0.1379	Tourism Distribution	0.0414	0.0455
		Tourism Pressure	0.0138	0.0138
		Tourism Spending	0.0828	0.0828
Socio-economic	0.1034	Demographics	0.0138	0.0124
		Education	0.0138	0.0124
		Employment	0.0138	0.0138
		GDP	0.0138	0.0138
		Household	0.0103	0.0093
		Response Capacity	0.0241	0.0217
		Vulnerable Population	0.0138	0.0124
Health	0.0862	Healthcare system	0.0517	0.0414
		Population	0.0345	0.0345
Infrastructure	0.1207	Basic Infrastructure	0.0181	0.0163
		Digital	0.0121	0.0109
		Disaster Response	0.0302	0.0302
		Energy & water	0.0302	0.0272
		Transport	0.0302	0.0272
Agriculture	0.0690	Farmland	0.0345	0.0379
		Land-use	0.0345	0.0345
Ecosystems	0.1034	Air & Water Quality	0.0352	0.0387
		Protected Areas	0.0341	0.0376
		Sustainable Tourism	0.0341	0.0341
	1		1	1

Figure 26: Weightings for the question of how important the indicator is to the tourism sector to withstand or recover from the event.

Each of the prioritised tourism resilience indicators identified in the above table are available as geospatial data at either a NUTS2 or NUTS3 regional level across Europe from publicly available sources, such as the EU Tourism Dashboard and Eurostat. Each indicator or combination of indicators can therefore be overlaid with hazard maps to identify particularly vulnerable locations as well as better understand which tourism indicators could be targeted to improve resilience hazards, for example earthquakes or flood events. The weights can be improved by incorporating more expert judgement and the methodology is designed so that individual stakeholders can adjust the weights based on the details of the hazard event, by adjusting the numerical weights at the overall category level or the detailed indicator level.

2.6.3 Combined Scenarios

Based on the multi-hazard scenario of an earthquake occurring followed by a flood in the same location three months later, we have developed a methodology for identifying and accounting for changes in the importance of vulnerability indicators over time and as the result of a multi-hazard scenario.

How important is the indicator to the tourism sector to withstand or recover from the event?

Tier 1 (Category)	Base Weight (Category)	Tier 2 (Indicator)	Before EQ (Indicator)	After EQ (1 week)	After EQ (3 months)	After Flood (1-day)
Basic Tourism Descriptors	0.1724	Basic Data	0.0345	0.0361	0.0340	0.0372
		Tourism Capacity	0.1379	0.1577	0.1358	0.1625
Tourist Risks	0.2069	Safety & Security	0.2069	0.2169	0.2038	0.2031
Socio-economic (Tourism)	0.1379	Tourism Distribution	0.0414	0.0473	0.0408	0.0447
		Tourism Pressure	0.0138	0.0118	0.0136	0.0149
		Tourism Spending	0.0828	0.0631	0.0815	0.0731
Socio-economic	0.1034	Demographics	0.0138	0.0145	0.0136	0.0149
		Education	0.0138	0.0131	0.0136	0.0135
		Employment	0.0138	0.0131	0.0136	0.0135
		GDP	0.0138	0.0145	0.0136	0.0163
		Household	0.0103	0.0099	0.0102	0.0102
		Response Capacity	0.0241	0.0322	0.0238	0.0284
		Vulnerable Population	0.0138	0.0158	0.0163	0.0179
Health	0.0862	Healthcare system	0.0517	0.0641	0.0509	0.0559
		Population	0.0345	0.0394	0.0340	0.0372
Infrastructure	0.1207	Basic Infrastructure	0.0181	0.0207	0.0214	0.0235
		Digital	0.0121	0.0115	0.0119	0.0130
		Disaster Response	0.0302	0.0374	0.0297	0.0355
		Energy & water	0.0302	0.0316	0.0297	0.0267
		Transport	0.0302	0.0374	0.0386	0.0424
Agriculture	0.0690	Farmland	0.0345	0.0164	0.0340	0.0169
		Land-use	0.0345	0.0164	0.0340	0.0271
Ecosystems	0.1034	Air & Water Quality	0.0352	0.0302	0.0346	0.0380
		Protected Areas	0.0341	0.0260	0.0336	0.0168
		Sustainable Tourism	0.0341	0.0228	0.0336	0.0168
	1		1	1	1	1

Figure 27: Detailed weightings at Tier 1 and Tier 2 for the tourism vulnerability index. The changing weightings indicate the changing importance at different stages of the earthquake-flood scenario.

As illustrated in the table above, the importance of tourism indicators often changes depending on the event in question and the stage of recovery. The importance of infrastructure and health indicators are increased in the aftermath of disasters as more stress is placed on the transport and

healthcare system, whereas the importance of agriculture and ecosystems by comparison are reduced in the immediate aftermath of both the earthquake and flood events.

These insights can be brought into further stakeholder engagement in combination with the quantitative and semi-quantitative approaches, and also provides a way to tie in stakeholder engagement into future scenarios / development plan scenarios, such as in the Canary Islands.

2.7 Direct and Indirect Risk Scenarios on a Local Scale – An example of Canary Islands

2.7.1 Introduction to Canary Islands Scenarios

In the Canary Islands pilot, direct and indirect risk impacts are being produced using both qualitative and quantitative approaches. This pilot will examine the following two multi-hazard scenarios, and their impact on the tourism infrastructure of La Palma: H1: Volcanic eruption (based on Cumbre Vieja eruption in La Palma 2021) for current conditions; and H2: Volcanic eruption in 2050 after a sequence of drought and interactions with climate and socioeconomic change.

A participatory process is to be adopted for the validation of the choice risk outputs, indicators and weights, with experts and stakeholders in the Canary Islands in close coordination with WP3 (ULL) for subsequent application by decision-makers in La Palma. The 2021 volcanic eruption will serve as a benchmark for the preliminary assessment of the Scorecard, offering a tangible reference point. The following provides a brief description of the quantitative, semi-quantitative and qualitative approaches depicted in Figure 28:

- Quantitative Modelling (Risk Outputs): Quantitative risk modelling in WP5 will be employed to assess direct and systemic vulnerabilities and risks for the tourism sector's infrastructure. This will include estimations of potential impacts such as the number of affected hotels and attractions, the extent of damage to transport and power infrastructure, and potential loss of connectivity. Interdependencies within the tourism sector of La Palma, as well as with the energy and agricultural sectors, will be considered to quantify the augmented economic losses from such inter-sectoral interactions.
- Semi-quantitative Modelling (Destination Vulnerability Composite Index): Complementing the quantitative analysis, a semi-quantitative approach as part of WP5-WP4 will be utilised to appraise dynamic vulnerabilities at the destination scale. This approach will factor in sensitivities within the tourism sector and other determinants such as population, economic stability, environmental factors, and infrastructure robustness. The selection of indicators will be informed through close collaboration in WP4 through the development of *VulneraTour*, a database of vulnerability drivers for tourism destinations, which categorises vulnerability drivers from scientific literature to assess resilience against natural hazards, providing crucial insights for disaster risk management and enhancing destination-specific strategies. Vulnerability indicators, particularly pertinent to the tourism sector's susceptibility in La Palma to volcanic activities and drought, and their linkages to agriculture and energy, will be selected. These indicators will be weighted and aggregated through a participatory approach with local experts and stakeholders using the AHP approach described in Sections 2.4.2 and 2.6.2 to provide an "Impact Factor," which will in turn be combined with the direct risk outputs to provide an "integrated risk" score for the various administrative divisions within La Palma.
- Qualitative Approach (Destination Resilience Scorecard): In a parallel, qualitative approach, a Destination Resilience Scorecard has been devised for tourism stakeholders and decision makers, focusing on governance aspects pertinent to managing risks and resilience within the destination. The Scorecard has been anchored in the priorities of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction to provide a policy lens aligned with internationally agreed-upon risk reduction criteria relevant to tourism stakeholders. According, the Scorecard has been contextualised through the tourism lens and addresses conditions in La Palma, particularly incorporating the forensic disaster analysis and its impacts on the tourism-agriculture nexus conducted by ULL for the volcanic eruptions in La Palma. The Scorecard

encompasses five dimensions from risk comprehension to the implementation of long-term resilience strategies.

Figure 28: Integration of quantitative, semi-quantitative and qualitative approaches for the Canary Islands Pilot.

Figure 29 further illustrates the methodology for integrating risk outputs from the two hazard scenarios used in the Canary Islands pilot with the semi-quantitative and qualitative approaches to arrive at an “Integrated Resilience Score” for La Palma through a comprehensive assessment framework. The general methodology for the calculation for the Integrated Resilience Score has been described in section 2.4.1.

For the Canary Island pilot, the following two hazard scenarios are used to quantify direct risk indicators in terms of: Capital Loss to Accommodations, Damage to Transportation, Damage to Power and Water Networks.

- **Hazard Scenario 1 (H1):** Volcanic eruption under current conditions, based on the 2021 Cumbre Vieja eruption in La Palma.
- **Hazard Scenario 2 (H2):** Volcanic eruption in 2050 after a sequence of droughts, influenced by climate and socioeconomic changes.

Figure 29: The Integrated Resilience Score (IRS) based on the interaction between the quantitative and qualitative “Tourism Resilience Scorecard” indicators.

2.7.2 Hazard Scenarios

The first hazard scenario is based on the 2021 Tajogaite eruption of the Cumbre Vieja on La Palma, Canary Islands, under current conditions. This long-lasting and hybrid eruption with pulsatory activity started on September 19, 2021, and concluded on December 13, 2021, lasting nearly three months. It followed a 50-year period of volcanic quiescence since the previous eruption in 1971 and is the longest and most damaging eruption recorded on La Palma. The inherently multi-hazard eruption led to lava flows, degassing, and ash fall, resulting in the evacuation of approximately 8,000 people, damage to over 2,800 buildings, 1,000 hectares of plantations, and approximately 92 km of roads. Tephra fallout temporarily closed La Palma airport and airports on neighbouring islands. This multi-hazard event severely impacted the tourism, agrifood, water, and energy sectors.

The eruption is well-documented, providing abundant data for scenario development. Ash fall is simulated using Fall3D, a software that models the atmospheric dispersal and deposition of tephra particles based on a 3D Eulerian model. Input parameters include atmospheric data (ERA5), total

grain size distribution (Bonadonna et al., 2023), mass flow rate, density, and plume height (Bonadonna et al., 2022; Reyes-Hardy et al., 2024; Biass et al., 2023). Fall3D outputs four parameters: deposit thickness, ground load, and average and flight-level ash concentration.

2.7.3 Direct Risk Outputs

By integrating socioeconomic datasets on population, GDP, buildings, and infrastructure, the exposure and damage from the simulated volcanic eruption can be estimated by superimposing the different data layers. Relevant datasets have been collected and reviewed (Ferrer and Herrera, 2024; Esch et al., 2022; Wang and Sun, 2022; Gao, 2020).

The second hazard scenario is a projection to 2050, similar to the first scenario but with the addition of a preceding drought event. This future scenario aims to illustrate the impact past events will have under future climate and socioeconomic conditions.

The scenario is to be done using the following process:

1. A typical drought season from 2010-2025, is exacerbated by the indices via an RCP245, 370 and 585 average, in order to create drought conditions in 2050 (via a 2040-2060 average). Various drought indices (growing season length, warm spell index, wet_precip_accumulation, pr10, maximum consecutive dry days, kbdi, are calculated to create the conditions impacting the islands.
2. The scenario conditions are then benchmarked against existing drought studies (WRI AQUEDUCT, C3S and various CMIP6 downscaled runs).
3. The volcano scenario (run as closely to the original run) is then run for a 2050-adjusted exposure and the drought conditions to look at and assess the impacts of the additional impacts to tourism, food security, water management, agriculture and the other effects where drought impacts occur.

2.7.4 Integrated Resilience Score (Quantitative)

The Quantitative Integrated Resilience Score utilises publicly available socio-economic, infrastructure, environmental and tourism exposure data, to produce a spatiotemporal diagnostic of integrated tourism resilience score at the municipality-level. Table 6 shows, as example, a list of suggested descriptors to be used in the estimation of the physical risk, social-economic, infrastructure, environmental and tourism vulnerability indices; nevertheless, depending on the available information and its quality, they can be modified and even extended. A database of indicators is currently being collected for La Palma. An important starting point for this is the comprehensive assessment of exposure layers by Ferrer and Herrera (2024) which has been shared with MYRIAD-EU. At this stage it is important to note that the selection of the final descriptors must ensure that the indicators and their weights are validated by local experts working in WP3.

Table 6: Example of physical risk, social-economic, and lack of resilience descriptors.

Index	Descriptors
Physical Damage/Loss	Capital Stock Loss - Accommodations
	Agricultural Production Loss
	Tourism Income Loss
	Transportation Damage
	Power Network Damage
Socio-Economic	Tourist Population Density
	Local Community Vulnerability (Age, Income, ...)
	Women in Workforce
	Mobility
	Crime
	Education
	Housing and Basic Utilities
Infrastructure	Insurance Coverage
	Tourism Pressure
	Tourism Infrastructure Utilization

	Traffic Congestion
	Public Transportation
	Healthcare Infrastructure
	Transportation (Density and Accessibility)
	Water Usage
	Green Infrastructure
Environmental	Share of Protected Areas
	Biodiversity (Terrestrial and Aquatic)
	Water Scarcity
	Air Quality Index
	Cultural Heritage / Cultural Assets
Tourism	Seasonality
	Tourism Density/Concentration
	Tourism Capacity
	Tourism Diversity
	Economic Reliance on Tourism
	Economic Reliance on Agriculture

2.7.5 Tourism Resilience Scorecard (Qualitative)

In addition to the quantitative score, the IRS framework is designed to include a comprehensive qualitative assessment of La Palma’s tourism institutions in terms of their capacities and performance to identify, reduce, manage, and finance disaster risk. As such, the Destination Resilience Scorecard was developed to measure and monitor the resilience of tourism stakeholders for the two multi-hazard scenarios (H1 and H2) through five critical success factors (CSFs) and 19 corresponding performance criteria (PCs). This comprehensive tool assesses stakeholder awareness, preparedness, and response capabilities, aiming to ensure sustainable and resilient tourism development. Table 7 provides a summary of the key CSFs and PCs, and more detailed descriptions including the overall evaluation questions and performance criteria are presented in Appendix E – Tourism resilience scorecard.

The evaluation of the Destination Resilience Scorecard is based on a participatory process, and stakeholder workshops to capture local processes for decision-making are planned together with ULL in WP3. This will ensure the production of relevant indicators and achievable targets that are representative of local knowledge, conditions, and context. This holistic approach helps in understanding and enhancing tourism destination resilience, ensuring that stakeholders can make informed decisions to protect and sustain tourism infrastructure and services. The Tourism Resilience Scorecard supports the continuous monitoring of risks, preparedness, response, and recovery strategies, ultimately contributing to more resilient tourism destinations.

Table 7: Critical Success Factors and Indicators representing the Destination Resilience Scorecard (draft to be validated with local stakeholders and experts).

CSF	Indicator Name	Description of Indicator
CSF1: Understanding Risks to Tourism	Perceived Risks to Tourism	Evaluates stakeholder perceptions of volcanic risks to tourism.
	Impacts on Tourism	Assesses understanding of both immediate and long-term volcanic impacts on tourism.
	Physical and Financial Risks	Measures awareness and preparedness for physical and financial risks from volcanoes.
	Tourism Integration in Disaster Plans	Examines how tourism concerns are incorporated into disaster risk management.
CSF2: Planning and Prioritization	Budget and Regulations	Focuses on the alignment of financial and regulatory support for volcanic resilience.
	Risk Integration in Policy	Looks at how volcanic risks are factored into tourism policies and plans.
	Business Continuity Planning	Evaluates the effectiveness of continuity and disaster recovery planning for tourism.
	Resilience Commitment	Assesses the commitment to integrating volcanic risk management into tourism agendas.
CSF3: Preparedness and Mitigation	Collaboration on Resilience	Measures the extent of collaboration in resilience strategies against volcanic risks.
	Early Warning Systems	Assesses the effectiveness of early warning systems tailored for tourism.
	Resilient Infrastructure	Reviews the promotion and investment in resilient tourism infrastructure.
	Training and Awareness	Evaluates training and awareness initiatives for managing volcanic impacts.
CSF4: Response and Recovery	Crisis Communication	Analyses the effectiveness of communication strategies during volcanic crises.
	Response and Recovery	Assesses the effectiveness of emergency responses to volcanic events.
	Resilience Initiatives	Measures the extent of initiatives aimed at protecting tourism assets.
CSF5: Long Term Resilience Actions	Investment and Diversification	Focuses on investments made for long-term resilience measures in tourism.
	Long-term Resilience Enhancement	Evaluates the effectiveness of policies and initiatives for long-term resilience to volcanic activities.
	Resilience Standards and Funds	Assesses compliance with resilience standards and the allocation of funds for supporting these standards in tourism businesses.
	Climate Impact Reduction	Focuses on measures to reduce the climate impact of tourism and efforts for long-term climate change mitigation.

3 How the methods fit into the framework?

This section provides an overview of how the methods developed in WP5 can support in the execution of the steps of the in MYRIAD-EU framework for systemic multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment and management. The framework consists of six steps (for a detailed description, see deliverable 2.3 and Hochrainer-Stigler et al. (2023)).

1. Finding a system definition
2. Characterization of direct risk
3. Characterization of indirect risk
4. Evaluation of direct and indirect risk
5. Defining risk management options
6. Accounting for future system state

3.1 Step 1: Finding a System Definition

For our analysis of systemic risks across Europe, we have defined specific regions and sectors to better understand and address the challenges they face. This analysis spans five pilot regions, namely the Canary Islands, Danube, North Sea, Scandinavia, and Veneto, and targets six critical sectors: Ecosystems & Forestry, Energy, Finance, Food & Agriculture, Infrastructure & Transport, and Tourism. By allowing the user to specify a region and sector the software enables the user to define their own system for generating multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios.

Datasets for European Scale and Pilot Regions

The identification of relevant datasets is crucial for understanding the risks that could impact the system under study. The risk analysis draws upon the following datasets in its analysis of risks for each region and sector.

1. Hazard Sets on a European Scale
 - Historical Hazard Footprints + Locations
 - Stochastic Event Sets of Relevance
 - Probabilistic Event Sets of Relevance
 - MYRIAD-HESA
 - Further Multi-Hazard Event Sets
2. Exposure Sets on a European Scale for use in risk modelling
3. Vulnerability Sets on a European Scale per hazard (Extracted Database and usage method)
4. Risk Sets on a European Scale
5. Historical Losses on a European Scale

3.2 Step 2: Characterisation of Direct Risk

Generic Direct Damage Methodology

Understanding and defining individual hazards is crucial for quantifying direct impacts. Figure 17 illustrates how direct impacts are calculated in the risk module and incorporation of this methodology was a critical step in software development. The basic model components are hazard, exposure, and vulnerability of any exposed elements, which transfers through to risk of direct impacts.

Hazard sets will be applied to single and multiple regions:

- Impacts of remote hazards on pilot regions
- Impacts of local hazards on other EU countries
- Reference for indirect effects of local hazards
- Comparison of importance of direct and indirect effects

Stochastic Event Set Production

The characterisation of direct risk through stochastic event set production is crucial for understanding potential damages from discrete events over time. By employing models that simulate different scenarios, this approach provides valuable metrics to help quantify expected

losses and identify risk thresholds, thereby facilitating better planning and risk management strategies in various sectors.

Sectoral Direct Damage Methodology

To evaluate the direct risks associated with various sectors effectively, we utilise a detailed Sectoral Direct Damage Methodology. The following illustrates the sectors we consider along with the potential metrics associated with direct impacts in each sector.

Table 8: Direct metrics calculated as part of WP5 at European and local scales.

Sector	Direct metrics calculated as part of MYRIAD WP5
Finance	Investment & Built Stocks: Replacement, Reconstruction, Depreciated Cost, Insurance Cost, Contents Included. A21 Capital Stock damage (AAL, Scenario, PML)
Infrastructure & Energy	Useability and Damage Analysis (length damaged), % Network Connectivity Loss (Canary implementation)
Food & Agriculture	Direct crop and livestock damage
Tourism	Hotel damage, Capital damage
Ecosystems & Forestry	Direct Environmental Impact
Cross Sector	Fatality & Disruption Functions, Displacement Functions, Sectoral Capital Damage

3.3 Step 3: Characterisation of Indirect Risk

To accurately assess the broader economic and societal impacts of natural hazards, our methodology includes a general model for evaluating indirect losses. Below is an overview of our approach:

Indirect Risk Methodology:

- General model for indirect losses (see section 2.5.2)

Inter-European Indirect Impacts:

- Models with pan-European capability
- Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) (Danube and Europe)
- GRACE (Scandinavian Pilot)
- Multiregional Impact Assessment Model (MRIA)

3.4 Evaluation of Direct and Indirect Risks

We developed an integrated approach to evaluating the direct and indirect risks. The methodology used in the software will therefore combine a semi-quantitative baseline resilience index with qualitative resilience scorecard assessments, resulting in a comprehensive analysis of resilience. Such a comprehensive approach is important for capturing nuanced aspects of resilience, aiding organisations and policymakers in developing targeted strategies to enhance their preparedness and response capabilities across different scenarios and sectors.

- Semi-Quantitative baseline resilience index uses a multi-dimensional approach focusing on social, economic, institutional, and infrastructural resilience.
- Qualitative resilience scorecard assessments for capturing different dimensions of resilience across the sectors.

3.5 Risk Management

The MYRIAD-EU Software will not generate risk management recommendations; however, the scenarios generated through the software can help decision makers better understand their risk to hazard impacts, which is a key step in prioritising potential risk management solutions.

3.6 Accounting for Future System State

To ensure a comprehensive understanding of how future climatic conditions might impact the system, we integrate a variety of advanced climate models. Climatic hazards present complex challenges that vary widely from extreme cold events to wildfires and droughts. Figure 1 is a list of climate-related hazards that can be potentially analysed through the software and future scenarios projected by the models linked to the software.

4 Key challenges and opportunities

One of the main scientific challenges within WP5 has been the need to integrate all types of data across multiple sectors and locations.

The production of single hazard models is complex, with many intricacies that still have data deficiencies when producing quantitative models. When looking at the quality of quantitative data, there are many techniques for quantifying the uncertainty or error bounds which have been used in a multi-risk context (Bayesian Networks, Markov chains etc. – Mohan et al., 2021), however if both qualitative and quantitative data need to be integrated into a model to inform a decision within a sector, we need a new method that brings expert information, the behaviour of the sector, humans, goals and beliefs into the analysis. Such a method has been proposed and described in this report.

The use of multi-agent models as part of the indirect loss modelling shows the strengths and this inherent lack of ability to downscale where data is inadequate (especially on employment and economic flows).

When starting the project, there was a clear limited sectoral view of risk modelling – catering to the commonly modelled buildings and engineering structures, but with little appreciation for the depth of interactions of a particular sector or for the processes and hierarchies within that sector. In the academic sphere we often produce models to test certain theories, imposing them on the sector as a possible solution with little interaction beforehand with the sector or end user of our solution. This is useful in many ways, but when moving towards multi-risk can often lead to the production of a barrier, and thus a lack of use of the model or method produced.

As part of the MYRIAD-EU framework, although it has been difficult to quantify sectoral multi-risk in a quantitative way for many risk metrics, the concepts of variability, complexity and other influences have led us to a more integrated approach, and it is important to focus on the following key questions:

- For whom are we producing the multi-risk models and how are we producing them? Has there been previous sectoral interaction and stakeholder interaction?
- How can measures of resiliency, reliability and vulnerability be used to monitor and more effectively manage the sector taking into account the sectoral hierarchy (i.e. tourism sphere of DMCs, hotels, governments, tourists)?
- What possible changes in current or future conditions (i.e. sudden climatic shifts or behavioural changes) could render data-driven models irrelevant and push for the need for a more holistic multi-risk approach for the sectors?
- What methods (modelling or otherwise) are needed to cope with today and tomorrow's complex, uncertain and variable conditions?
- What additional data collection (i.e. quantitative metrics for the sector, survey data) is needed so that changes can be identified?

The opportunity exists to build sectoral solutions to multi-hazard impacts rather than focussing on a one-size-fits-all analytic product. The inherent lack of data in different sectors, or certain locations or the complexity of processes can be on one hand handled through a sequenced solution of potential pathways. Another important method uses semi-quantitative and qualitative indices in tandem with quantitative models. In this way, whatever data-driven analytics can be undertaken are performed while the stakeholder-derived semi-quantitative and qualitative indices are used to give recommendations and ratings.

Every location and hazard have different levels, time scales, data needs and methods depending on the location. Such process diagrams have been presented by Tilloy et al. (2019) and as part of the MATRIX and NARSIS projects, where different levels of complexity for a site are used to evaluate the multi-hazard interactions. When bringing it through to sectoral risks, the complexity ends up as one of a 4-dimensional problem.

Explaining these processes to stakeholders in their own words/, sectoral meanings and beliefs is key to an effective take up of multi-risk solutions. No manner of analytical modelling replaces the human and company complexity of a particular sector straddling the societal, government, business and environmental influences, and the difficulties of having a clear view or knowledge to understand the complexities within it.

5 Take up of research output outside of MYRIAD-EU

5.1 Contribution to the Expected Impacts of the Call

The contribution of the work executed in WP5 towards the expected impacts as foreseen in the Call text (marked in *italics* below) and the project's Grant Agreement have been evaluated as part of this deliverable.

"...consensus in better definitions, indicators and functions to characterise multi-hazard risk through enhanced inter-disciplinary collaboration..."

WP5 has contributed to the Disaster Risk Gateway and through increased interaction with the Hazard Information Profiles, improved indicators at EU and local scale and production of functions and sets across different stakeholder groups.

"...prioritisation of investments & selection of effective DRM options..." & "...enhanced risk-informed decisions ... addressing trade-offs between... options"

The WP5 scenarios and methods help to prioritise investments, but more importantly they help to integrate the concept of multi-hazard risk into the decision-making frame of the sectors with which we are working. In combination with the WP6 pathways methods, and the findings in WP4, better risk-informed decisions can be made at a sector level using different risk metrics.

Risklayer presented Hotel Resilient, an online platform for hotels, destination management companies (DMCs) and tour operators to collect, share and verify information on sustainable and resilience performance metrics globally. Risklayer has signed a number of MOUs with DMCs and Tour Operators to cooperate on further development and dissemination of the platform.

"...enhanced capacity for identification of vulnerable, threatened areas and infrastructures most at risk from multi hazards in Europe"

The exposure-at-risk model as well as the different EU scale contributions on direct and indirect risk as well as exposure and hazard allow for enhanced capacity for identification of vulnerable, threatened areas and infrastructures most at risk from multi hazards in Europe. Risk assessments for different sectors can benefit from taking into account and comparing scenarios for the current state and scenarios for future climate change. The concepts of MYRIAD WP5 were used in an effort on understanding the probable maximum loss (PML) across multiple hazards for a set of 11 small island nations around the world for COP28

"...better informed forward-looking national risk assessments that take into account long-term drivers such as climate change...enhance implementation of existing legislation and streamlining of policies..."

Risklayer contributed to a COP28 report on "Risk sharing for Loss and Damage: Scaling up protection for the Global South" (Briefing Note: <https://www.cisl.cam.ac.uk/news-and-resources/publications/risk-sharing-loss-and-damage-scaling-protection-global-south>). Key recommendations include the establishment of pre-arranged finance facilities and umbrella stop-loss mechanisms to shield national economies from severe climate impacts, particularly focusing on least developed countries, small island developing states, and other vulnerable groups. This initiative seeks to provide immediate, scalable protection through strategic financial planning and risk sharing.

...

"...enhanced understanding of relationships and interactions of multiple hazards ... driven by ... changes on different time and spatial scales"

The methods detailed in the deliverable portray an enhanced understanding of relationships and interactions of multiple hazards driven by changes on different time and spatial scales, allowing for a temporal sequence of risk and hazard change over time. Significant take up of the overlapping

hazards work by Judith Claassen has been seen, with collaborations discussed in Section 2.1.5 of this report.

There have also been interactions with the World Bank Eastern Europe office regarding the multi-hazard scenarios being produced for the Danube, as the findings are of use in planning and benchmarking of other risk results for Romania. This provides useable numbers for the government in terms of planning disaster risk financing mechanisms.

“...better knowledge exchange through platforms such as DRMKC, and stakeholder networks on emergent risks and extreme events (e.g., Community of Users, Risk KAN)”

The findings of WP5 and the other technical WPs in the MYRIAD-EU project have been discussed, presented and exchanged with others through platforms, stakeholder events and communities of practice / conferences as shown below.

Changing World Risks

Risklayer attended the 3rd International Conference Natural Hazards and Risks in a Changing World (Changing World Risks 2024) in Amsterdam from June 12 – 13, 2024. Risklayer contributed to the conference by presenting the following four papers or tools:

- Demonstrating Multi-Hazard Risk Assessment Tools through MYRIAD-EU: A Journey Through Software Interplay and Challenges (tool demonstration)
- A digital Bento box for natural disaster, climate and multi-risk data: addressing the challenges and solutions for multi-risk data needs (tool demonstration)
- Volcanoes and tsunamis – multi-risk scenarios for tourism in the Canary Islands (paper)
- Analysing Tourism, Disaster Risk and Climate Change Data at the Sub-national Scale (paper)

The research presented showcased the WP5 of MYRIAD-EU project, including the work of Risklayer and other project partners. Risklayer also led a session at the conference on Demonstration of multi-hazard and multi-risk tools and services, with many of the attendees saying they plan to use the MYRIAD tools once available.

Understanding Risk

Risklayer attended Understanding Risk, presenting the Hotel Resilient tool, and also supporting the MYRIAD-EU multi-hazard session. Much interest was created within other sessions of the conference, especially around the need for tailored risk assessment metrics and scenarios for sectors rather than overly quantitative/theoretical modelling.

EGU

Interactions and outreach have been made each year at EGU with many institutions. As part of the EGU in 2024, a multi-hazard workshop was attended on remote sensing and multi-hazard EO4MULTIHA where insights were given from WP5 on hazard and risk scenarios.

Datasets and knowledge have also been shared with the MIRACA project regarding WP5 in addition to the Paratus Project. The direct impact scenarios thus far have been put up on the MacroMIP confluence page so that we can share them with many modellers. In addition, as part of the JRC DRMKC workshop, insights were given into multi-hazard analysis. Finally, an additional continued collaboration is the European Environmental Agency, with discussions as to how losses are affected as a result of multi-hazard and multi-risk definitions.

Risklayer attended the International Tourism Conference (ITB) in Berlin from March 5 – 7, 2024 with four staff. Bijan Khazai of Risklayer took part in the panel discussion “Technology for Sustainable Tourism Innovation”, discussing the need for tourism stakeholders to understand the

risks associated with their destinations and tourism assets. Trevor Girard of Risklayer took part in discussions with industry experts and helped draft a series of theses on Radical Changes in Tourism to make the industry more sustainable and resilient to internal and external threats, including natural hazards.

5.2 Sectoral Impacts

Infrastructure and transport

The forward-looking multi-risk scenarios can support assessment of the longer-term impacts of multiple risks on transport infrastructure and as a decision support tool for making investment decisions. There are no direct impacts to the infrastructure and transport sector to report at this time.

Food and agriculture

The forward-looking multi-risk scenarios can support assessment of the longer-term impacts of multiple risks on the food and agriculture sector. This is particularly important as the sector undergoes multiple non-homogeneous changes due to climate change. There are no direct impacts to the food and agriculture sector to report at this time.

Ecosystems and forestry

The forward-looking multi-risk scenarios can inform a better understanding of the consequences and costs of inaction in the ecosystems and forestry sector. There are no direct impacts to the ecosystems and forestry sector to report at this time.

Energy

MYRIAD-EU can enable the inventory and understanding of hazards on the energy system during and after the transition into a resilient and sustainable energy system. The systematic approach of hazard and risk inventory and presentation of the results via the hazard dashboard will enable energy system operators to effectively manage and improve the resilience of the system. There are no direct impacts to the energy sector to report at this time.

Finance

The production of a combined set of coinciding hazards allowed for an insurance mechanism to be produced in order to cover the largest events occurring in a number of countries. It was presented in multiple COP28 forums, and is being further developed into a useable product (Pelaez et al 2023). The completed report emphasizes utilizing risk capital markets to enhance financial protection against climate risks for vulnerable regions.

Often (re-)insurance companies still consider the hazards that their assets are exposed to as independent, not considering the potential risk and associated higher losses of multiple disasters occurring at the same time. One of the MYRIAD-EU stakeholders is AON, a well-known insurance company. At AON, they are currently trying to understand how perils are not independent and how their risks differ from single events. The output of MYRIAD-HESA has allowed AON to improve their scientific knowledge on potential multi-hazards that have occurred near their assets. They have particularly been able to get a better overview of the more unique multi-hazard interaction, such as earthquakes occurring in close succession with tropical storms.

In addition, the statistical dependencies between hazards that have been calculated using the VineCopulas package will be tested by Aon, such that they can better understand the likelihood of two extremes co-occurring. Using these dependencies AON can, for example, evaluate what the likelihood is that their asset will be affected by both extreme rainfall as well as extreme wind at the

same time. Such tools enable more informed decision-making for the future to better diversify their risk.

Tourism

Crisis Resilient Guidelines

The hospitality industry is highly susceptible to the impacts of natural hazards and climate change exacerbates natural hazards, including heatwaves, floods, windstorms, droughts and forest fires, through increased hazard frequency, intensity and altered geographic distribution. These escalating crisis and climate risks highlight the need for improved resilience in the hospitality industry. To meet this growing need Risklayer and MYRIAD-EU sectoral representative HOTREC have worked together to create Crisis Resilient Guidelines for the hospitality industry, including hotels, restaurants, cafés, and night-life entertainment venues. The aim of guidelines is to assist HOTREC members to better prepare, withstand and recover from crisis and climate related hazards. The focus is on crisis resilience, which prioritizes above all the safety of occupants and staff when faced with natural hazard events, while also implementing measures to maintain essential services and swiftly recover from disaster impacts. The first draft of the guidelines has been provided to HOTREC members for review. The review is ongoing but so far we have only received positive feedback.

Tourism Policy Brief

Risklayer is also writing a policy brief from the MYRIAD-EU project, in collaboration with HOTREC, The policy brief will provide critical guidance for national and local government stakeholders, as well as private sector entities in tourism and related sectors such as agriculture, energy, emergency management, infrastructure, and finance. This policy brief will serve as a comprehensive synthesis of the MYRIAD framework and tools, offering a detailed roadmap for building resilience in tourism destinations. The brief will outline the application of the MYRIAD framework, starting with the initial situational analysis of a destination to establish key priorities. It will cover the identification and measurement of direct and indirect risks, and how these metrics can be utilized to manage current risks while also preparing for future conditions driven by climate and socio-economic changes. By drawing on practical examples from the Canary Islands and Danube pilots, the brief will demonstrate the real-world application of these tools, offering stakeholders clear, actionable insights. This policy brief is particularly impactful as it will be the first of its kind, setting a precedent for future policy briefs within the MYRIAD-EU project. It aims to inform and guide the development of resilience strategies across sectors by providing a multi-risk and cross-sectoral approach. The insights gained from this document will be crucial for European stakeholders, offering a template for resilience planning that can be adapted and applied across different regions and sectors.

Resilient Destinations

Risklayer is organizing the upcoming session titled "Resilient Destinations: Empowering Local Governments Through Tourism-Led Disaster Risk Reduction" at the Asia-Pacific Ministerial Conference on Disaster Risk Reduction (APMCDRR) from October 16-18 2024 on behalf of the MYRIAD-EU Consortium. Risklayer will convene key stakeholders including the Secretary of Tourism of the Philippines, the Mayor of Quezon City, and the CEO of the Pacific Asia Travel Association (PATA) to address critical challenges and opportunities in building resilient tourism destinations. This session primarily targets a diverse group of stakeholders in the tourism and disaster risk reduction (DRR) sectors, including representatives from tourism organizations, local government officials, private sector stakeholders, and disaster risk management professionals.

The impact of this session will be in advancing the discourse on tourism-led disaster resilience which is novel at such an important venue with a competitive selection process for the nominated sessions. By showcasing the MYRIAD-EU framework and its application towards the tourism sector, the session will demonstrate the practical application of MYRIAD-EU research results in a real-world context. The session will also highlight the importance of multi-sectoral collaboration, a critical

focus of the MYRIAD-EU project and demonstrate tangible tools such as the software platform developed by Risklayer and the Scorecard cross-sectoral coordinated decision-making can enhance the resilience of a destination. This demonstration is expected to inspire similar initiatives in other cities and regions, particularly those in Asia-Pacific, where the tourism industry is both a vital economic driver and a sector vulnerable to disasters.

6 Future Research

From the key challenges and opportunities come many chances for future research in the field. Although a huge step is made within every EU project towards improving quantitative modelling processes of risk metrics in Europe for natural hazards, as has also been done in MYRIAD-EU, there still exists a huge amount of need for hazard, exposure, vulnerability and risk efforts across all hazards, especially with a focus on sectors.

There exist very few studies focussing on infrastructure, or ecosystems or indeed sectoral buildings and processes; with much of the focus on residential, commercial and industrial buildings with little splits. More work is needed to define sectors from a multi-risk perspective. This can often be done as part of a qualitative DAPP style of approach, however there is a need for more quantitative, and semi-quantitative processes accounting for the dynamics of the hazard, exposure and vulnerability contributing to the risk.

The following specific future research topics are proposed:

- Improved stakeholder engagement in the quantitative and semi-quantitative index approach for specific sectors.
- Simplified approaches for the integration of dynamic vulnerability pertaining to risk changes over a development plan period.
- Improved single hazard solutions for individual hazards including production of open scenario sets of historic events for use within multi-hazard and multi-risk applications.
- Further improvement of exposure sets for specific sectors across Europe after consultation with what is important for stakeholders in those sectors.
- Integrated process diagrams of the interactions between stakeholders for particular locations in sectors. The interactions between stakeholders and the scales (both temporal and spatial) often render traditional risk modelling solutions of little use for decision making. Further improvement is required in this field with the tools in WP4, WP5 and WP6 needing further outreach and further integration in coming years.

7 Conclusion

This report has detailed the development of methodologies for assessing multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios across Europe. It emphasises the integration of existing approaches to enhance risk quantification, focusing on creating comprehensive exposure metrics for various hazards like earthquakes, floods, volcanos and biological threats. The report discusses the extension of hazard data into multi-hazard frameworks, development of vulnerability data for direct and indirect scenarios, and evaluates different modelling approaches such as agent-based models and dynamic adaptive policy pathways. It concludes with the proposed integration of these methodologies into the MYRIAD-EU framework, setting the stage for implementing robust risk management strategies across Europe. We have integrated and enhanced existing methodologies to assess a variety of natural and human-made hazards, with a special focus on addressing multi-sector risks at the European level. Key components developed include sophisticated exposure metrics across vital sectors such as agriculture, tourism, infrastructure and socio-economic aspects.

The complexity of creating plausible temporal sequences for hazard interactions and accurately assigning return periods to these events adds a significant layer of complexity to our models. Moreover, the dynamic nature of these hazards introduces substantial uncertainty, particularly when modelling damaging events such as volcanic eruptions. Establishing impact-relevant thresholds and predicting future changes in vulnerability further complicate the assessments, as does obtaining precise data for exposure analysis, such as time-of-day data for tourist movements.

In addressing these challenges, we have employed robust methodologies for both direct and indirect risk scenarios, including agent-based models, dynamic adaptive policy pathways, and computational general equilibrium models. These methods have been critically evaluated to offer a comprehensive view of the modelling landscape, supplemented by empirical and machine learning methods to enhance the simulation of risk scenarios.

This work has practical applications, extending beyond theory to practical applications for European disaster risk management initiatives. The integration of comprehensive multi-hazard and multi-risk assessments promises to enhance the resilience of European communities against a wide array of risks, fostering a proactive approach to disaster risk management and planning. However, quantifying the effectiveness of Disaster Risk Reduction measures remains challenging due to policy shifts and complex interactions between sectors and hazards. The report emphasises the reliance on high-quality data for exposure, hazard, and vulnerability from various sources, underlining the need for datasets that are tailored to the diverse sectors involved in MYRIAD-EU. These datasets must be adaptable to changing conditions and detailed enough to capture the dynamics of multi-hazard risks for both current and future scenarios.

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Appendix A – Additional Risk Concepts

Duration of 60 days																
Return Period (years)	1	2	5	10	20	50	100	200	250	500	1000	2000	2500	5000	10000	Hazard 1
1	0.280027	0.218396	0.178912	0.165313	0.158429	0.154271	0.152881	0.152185	0.152045	0.151767	0.151627	0.151558	0.151544	0.151516	0.151502	
2	0.218396	0.151488	0.108625	0.093861	0.086388	0.081874	0.080365	0.079609	0.079458	0.079155	0.079004	0.078929	0.078913	0.078883	0.078868	
5	0.178912	0.108625	0.063596	0.048087	0.040236	0.035494	0.033909	0.033115	0.032956	0.032638	0.032479	0.0324	0.032384	0.032352	0.032336	
10	0.165313	0.093861	0.048087	0.03232	0.02434	0.01952	0.017908	0.017101	0.016939	0.016616	0.016454	0.016374	0.016358	0.016325	0.016309	
20	0.158429	0.086388	0.040236	0.02434	0.016293	0.011433	0.009808	0.008994	0.008831	0.008506	0.008343	0.008261	0.008245	0.008212	0.008196	
50	0.154271	0.081874	0.035494	0.01952	0.011433	0.006549	0.004916	0.004098	0.003935	0.003607	0.003444	0.003362	0.003346	0.003313	0.003296	
100	0.152881	0.080365	0.033909	0.017908	0.009808	0.004916	0.00328	0.002461	0.002297	0.001969	0.001805	0.001723	0.001707	0.001674	0.001658	
200	0.152185	0.079609	0.033115	0.017101	0.008994	0.004098	0.002461	0.001641	0.001477	0.001149	0.000985	0.000903	0.000887	0.000854	0.000837	
250	0.152045	0.079458	0.032956	0.016939	0.008831	0.003935	0.002297	0.001477	0.001313	0.000985	0.000821	0.000739	0.000723	0.00069	0.000673	
500	0.151767	0.079155	0.032638	0.016616	0.008506	0.003607	0.001969	0.001149	0.000985	0.000657	0.000493	0.000411	0.000394	0.000361	0.000345	
1000	0.151627	0.079004	0.032479	0.016454	0.008343	0.003444	0.001805	0.000985	0.000821	0.000493	0.000328	0.000246	0.00023	0.000197	0.000181	
2000	0.151558	0.078929	0.0324	0.016374	0.008261	0.003362	0.001723	0.000903	0.000739	0.000411	0.000246	0.000164	0.000148	0.000115	9.86E-05	
2500	0.151544	0.078913	0.032384	0.016358	0.008245	0.003346	0.001707	0.000887	0.000723	0.000394	0.00023	0.000148	0.000131	9.86E-05	8.21E-05	
5000	0.151516	0.078883	0.032352	0.016325	0.008212	0.003313	0.001674	0.000854	0.00069	0.000361	0.000197	0.000115	9.86E-05	6.57E-05	4.93E-05	
10000	0.151502	0.078868	0.032336	0.016309	0.008196	0.003296	0.001658	0.000837	0.000673	0.000345	0.000181	9.86E-05	8.21E-05	4.93E-05	3.29E-05	
Hazard 2																
Duration of 6 years																
Return Period (years)	1	2	5	10	20	50	100	200	250	500	1000	2000	2500	5000	10000	Hazard 1
1	0.999994	0.999876	0.99925	0.998633	0.998156	0.997792	0.997656	0.997585	0.99757	0.997541	0.997526	0.997518	0.997517	0.997514	0.997513	
2	0.999876	0.997511	0.984961	0.972609	0.963033	0.955748	0.953014	0.951584	0.951293	0.950705	0.950409	0.95026	0.95023	0.95017	0.95014	
5	0.99925	0.984961	0.909133	0.834497	0.776641	0.732623	0.716101	0.707461	0.705702	0.702152	0.70036	0.699461	0.69928	0.69892	0.698739	
10	0.998633	0.972609	0.834497	0.698558	0.59318	0.513008	0.482915	0.467178	0.463974	0.457508	0.454245	0.452606	0.452278	0.451621	0.451292	
20	0.998156	0.963033	0.776641	0.59318	0.450963	0.342764	0.302152	0.280914	0.276589	0.267862	0.263459	0.261248	0.260805	0.259918	0.259474	
50	0.997792	0.955748	0.732623	0.513008	0.342764	0.213243	0.164627	0.139204	0.134027	0.12358	0.118309	0.115662	0.115131	0.11407	0.113538	
100	0.997656	0.953014	0.716101	0.482915	0.302152	0.164627	0.113007	0.086013	0.080516	0.069423	0.063827	0.061016	0.060453	0.059326	0.058761	
200	0.997585	0.951584	0.707461	0.467178	0.280914	0.139204	0.086013	0.058197	0.052533	0.041103	0.035336	0.03244	0.031859	0.030698	0.030116	
250	0.99757	0.951293	0.705702	0.463974	0.276589	0.134027	0.080516	0.052533	0.046835	0.035336	0.029535	0.026621	0.026037	0.024868	0.024283	
500	0.997541	0.950705	0.702152	0.457508	0.267862	0.12358	0.069423	0.041103	0.035336	0.023698	0.017827	0.014878	0.014287	0.013104	0.012512	
1000	0.997526	0.950409	0.70036	0.454245	0.263459	0.118309	0.063827	0.035336	0.029535	0.017827	0.01192	0.008954	0.008359	0.007169	0.006574	
2000	0.997518	0.95026	0.699461	0.452606	0.261248	0.115662	0.061016	0.03244	0.026621	0.014878	0.008954	0.005978	0.005382	0.004188	0.003591	
2500	0.997517	0.95023	0.69928	0.452278	0.260805	0.115131	0.060453	0.031859	0.026037	0.014287	0.008359	0.005382	0.004785	0.003591	0.002993	
5000	0.997514	0.95017	0.69892	0.451621	0.259918	0.11407	0.059326	0.030698	0.024868	0.013104	0.007169	0.004188	0.003591	0.002395	0.001797	
10000	0.997513	0.95014	0.698739	0.451292	0.259474	0.113538	0.058761	0.030116	0.024283	0.012512	0.006574	0.003591	0.002993	0.001797	0.001198	
Hazard 2																

Figure 30: Examples of overlapping hazard joint probabilities for independent events for a certain duration.

Appendix B – Exposure data sets and sectors

Table 9: Overview of available population datasets.

Data Set/Model	Asset Type	Resolution	Author(s)	Description
GHS-POP (2023A vers)	Population Grid	Multitemporal	JRC	The GHSL Data Package 2023 includes multitemporal products from 1975 through 2020, and future projections for 2025 and 2030. It offers insights into human presence using data from Sentinel-2, Landsat, and global DEM data. Including the ENACT dataset for usage in temporal settings (day/night, and monthly)
HRSL (30m)	Population Grid	30m	Facebook	The High Resolution Settlement Layer (HRSL) from Facebook provides human population distribution estimates for the year 2015 at a resolution of 30m, based on recent census data and high-resolution satellite imagery.
Kontur (400m)	Population Grid	400m	Kontur	Kontur Population dataset uses H3 hexagons to represent population counts. It is based on GHSL data, Facebook population data (HRSL), Microsoft Building Footprint, Land Information New Zealand, and Copernicus Global Land Service data.
GEOSTAT	Population Grid	1km	EC	GEOSTAT provides population data on a 1km square grid. The 2021 Census presented key census topics on an EU-wide 1 km square grid, allowing for flexible cross-border analysis.
EUROSTAT CENSUS GRID 2021	Census Data	1km	EC	The 2021 Census data are available on an EU-wide 1 km square grid, offering a more detailed and flexible analysis tailored to research or policy needs.
GFZ	Exposure Data	NUTS3	Steinhausen, M.; Schröter, K.; Lüdtke, S.; Drews, M.	European exposure data for BN-FLEMO models, including European asset map, residential building areas, and flood experience data.

WSF-3D Pop (12m-90m)	Building Data	90m	DLR	Quantification of buildings' average height, total volume, area, and fraction, using satellite imagery and radar data.
Landscan (1km)	Population Grid	30 arc-seconds	Oak Ridge National Laboratory	Global model for population distribution based on land cover, slope, proximity to roads, and settlement locations.
WorldPop (100m), top-down constrained and unconstrained /GRID3	Population Data	High resolution (100m)	Tatem et al. (2023)	Data on population distributions and characteristics at high spatial resolution.
CIESIN GPW	Population Data	Various	CIESIN	Population estimates and densities for 1990 and 1995 on a 2.5' grid, adjusted to match United Nations national population estimates.
HANZE v2.0 1870-2020 (100m)	Land Cover/Use, Population, GDP, Assets	100m	Paprotny et al. (2023)	High-resolution maps of land cover/use, population, GDP, and fixed assets for 42 countries in Europe from 1870 to 2020.
Data for Good Mobility Data	Population movement	Various resolutions	Facebook	https://dataforgood.facebook.com/dfg/tools/movement-range-maps Mobility data during COVID - however other datasets exist
Maddison (2008) and country statistical offices	Population	Country	Maddison (2008) and country statistical offices	
Google Mobility Data	Population movement	Various resolutions	Google	https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/data_documentation.html?hl=en These reports detail the movement trends as Over time arranged by geographical areas and classified into various categories of places, such as shops and leisure spaces, supermarkets and pharmacies, parks, public transport stations, workplaces and residential areas.

SERA-EU	Exposure Models	Admin Level 1	Vitor Silva, Venetia Despotaki (GEM Foundation)	Development of exposure and vulnerability models for seismic risk reduction strategies in Europe, based on the latest national housing census data.
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The exposure component quantifies the elements at risk in the event of a natural hazard. This can be measured in various units, depending on the element and sector in question:

a. Infrastructure and Transport Sector (E_infra)

- Value: Monetary value or replacement cost of buildings, roads, bridges, etc.
- Elements: Number of buildings, length of roads, number of bridges, etc.
- Capacity: Daily traffic volume, transportation capacity, etc.
- People: Population using the infrastructure daily.

b. Food and Agriculture Sector (E_agri)

- Value: Market value of crops, livestock, and other agricultural assets.
- Elements: Number of farms, quantity of crops, headcount of livestock, etc.
- Area: Land area under cultivation, size of pastures, etc.
- Production: Volume of agricultural produce, productivity metrics.

c. Ecosystems and Forestry Sector (E_eco)

- Value: Economic valuation of ecosystem services.
- Elements: Number of species, conservation status.
- Area: Square kilometres of natural reserves, forests.
- Biodiversity: Biodiversity indices, habitat quality metrics.

d. Energy Sector (E_energy)

- Value: Valuation of energy-producing assets and reserves.
- Elements: Number and capacity of power plants, length of power lines.
- Capacity: Energy production and distribution capacity.
- People: Number of consumers served by the energy infrastructure.

e. Finance (including buildings) Sector (E_finance)

- Value: Economic value of financial assets, insured values of properties.
- Elements: Number of financial institutions, quantity of insured buildings.
- Transactions: Volume and value of financial transactions.
- People: Employees in the sector, number of customers.

f. Tourism Sector (E_tourism)

- Value: Revenue from tourism-related activities, replacement cost of hotels etc.
- Elements: Number of hotels, tourist attractions.
- Capacity: Visitor capacity, accommodation capacity.
- People: Number of tourists, employment in tourism.

Table 10: Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community Rev. 2 (2008): Level 1 Codes.

Code	Economic Area
A	Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing
B	Mining and Quarrying
C	Manufacturing
D	Electricity, Gas, Steam and Air Conditioning Supply
E	Water Supply; Sewerage, Waste Management and Remediation Activities
F	Construction
G	Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles
H	Transportation and Storage
I	Accommodation and Food Service Activities
J	Information and Communication
K	Financial and Insurance Activities
L	Real Estate Activities
M	Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities
N	Administrative and Support Service Activities
O	Public Administration and Defence; Compulsory Social Security
P	Education
Q	Human Health and Social Work Activities
R	Arts, Entertainment and Recreation
S	Other Service Activities
T	Activities of Households as Employers; Undifferentiated Goods and Services Producing Activities of Households for Own Use
U	Activities of Extraterritorial Organisations and Bodies

Figure 31: The different focus regions of MYRIAD-EU with the principal hazards and affected sectors.

Appendix C – Future scenarios

- **RCP2.6: Low Emission Scenario:** This scenario assumes significant mitigation efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, resulting in a peak and subsequent decline in radiative forcing. It is aimed at limiting global warming to below 2 °C above pre-industrial levels.
- **RCP4.5: Intermediate Scenario:** This scenario assumes that greenhouse gas emissions will stabilize through a combination of mitigation strategies and moderate economic growth.
- **RCP6.0: Intermediate Scenario:** This scenario assumes a stabilization of emissions through the implementation of some mitigation strategies, leading to a gradual increase in radiative forcing. It reflects a world with delayed but eventual policy actions to curb emissions.
- **RCP8.5: High Emission Scenario:** This scenario assumes continued increases in greenhouse gas emissions without significant efforts to mitigate them. It represents a "business as usual" approach with high population growth, limited technological change, and high energy demand.

The SSPs consider different future societal developments, such as population growth, economic development, and urbanisation, and is intended to complement the RCPs.

- **SSP1: Sustainability - Taking the green road:** The world progressively shifts towards a sustainable path, focusing on inclusive development that respects environmental boundaries
- **SSP2: Middle of the road:** The world continues along its historical patterns, with social, economic, and technological trends remaining steady. Development and income growth are uneven, with some countries making significant progress while others lag.
- **SSP3: Regional rivalry - A rocky road:** Rising nationalism, security concerns, and regional conflicts drive countries to prioritize domestic and regional issues. Policies increasingly focus on national and regional security.
- **SSP4: Inequality – A road divided:** Inadequate investment in human capital, combined with growing disparities in economic opportunity and political power, intensify inequalities and stratification within and between countries.
- **SSP5: Fossil-fueled development - Taking the highway:** The world relies on competitive markets, innovation, and participatory societies to achieve rapid technological progress and human capital development, viewing this as the path to sustainable development.

Table 11: Atmospheric variables used to calculate climate indicators.

STAC key	Description	Unit	Type
Tas	Daily Near-Surface Air Temperature	K	Netcdf
Tasmin	Daily Minimum Near-Surface Air Temperature	K	Netcdf
Tasmax	Daily Maximum Near-Surface Air Temperature	K	Netcdf
Pr	Precipitation	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Netcdf
sfcWind	Daily-Mean Near-Surface Wind Speed	m s ⁻¹	Netcdf
Hurs	Near-Surface Relative Humidity	%	Netcdf
Huss	Near-Surface Specific Humidity	1	Netcdf

Table 12: Climate and tourism indicators provided for MYRIAD-EU. The SSP scenarios refer to CMIP6 data, whereas the RCP scenarios refer to CMIP5 data.

Climate indicator	Description	Unit	Resolution	Pathways
tx10p	Number of days with maximum temperature below the 10th percentile	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)

tn10p	Number of days with minimum temperature below the 10th percentile	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
cold_spell_duration_index	Count of days with at least six consecutive days when the daily minimum temperature < 10th percentile	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
maximum_consecutive_dry_days	Maximum consecutive days with daily precipitation < 1 mm/d	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
maximum_consecutive_wet_days	Maximum consecutive days with daily precipitation >= 1 mm/d	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
daily_temperature_range	Mean diurnal temperature range	K	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
frost_days	Annual count of days when daily minimum temperature < 0°C.	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
growing_season_length	Number of days between the first occurrence of at least 6 consecutive days with mean daily temperature > 5°C and the first occurrence of at least 6 consecutive days with mean daily temperature < 5°C (after 7th January)	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
pr10	Days per year with precipitation >= 10mm (heavy precipitation days)	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
ice_days	Number of days with maximum daily temperature < 0°C	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
rx1day	Annual maximum 1-day total precipitation	mm	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
rx5day	Annual maximum 5-day total precipitation	mm	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
tx_max	Annual maximum of daily maximum temperature	K	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
tn_max	Annual maximum of daily minimum temperature	K	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
tx_min	Annual minimum of daily maximum temperature	K	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
tn_min	Annual minimum of daily minimum temperature	K	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245,

				ssp585 (2015-2100)
wetdays	Number of days per year with 1 mm or more precipitation	day	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
wet_precip_accumulation	Total accumulated precipitation over days where precipitation > 1 mm/day (annual amount of precipitation)	mm	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
tasmax25	Annual count of days when daily maximum temperature > 25 °C	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
tropical_nights	Annual count of days when daily minimum temperature > 20 °C	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
pr20	Days per year with precipitation >= 20mm (heavy precipitation days)	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
tx90p	Number of days with maximum temperature > 90th percentile	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
tn90p	Number of days with minimum temperature > 90th percentile	days	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
warm_spell_duration_index	Annual count of days with at least 6 consecutive days where the daily maximum temperature > 90th percentile	day	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
heat_index	Perceived temperature after relative humidity is considered (only valid for > 20 °C, dew point base of 14 °C)	°C	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
humindex	Describes the temperature felt by a person when relative humidity is considered (dew point of 7 °C)	°C	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
fire_weather_index	Numeric rating of fire intensity	-	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
fire_weather_index_annual_mean	Numeric rating of fire intensity annual average	-	25x25km	Historical (1950-2014), ssp245, ssp585 (2015-2100)
CIT_daily_index	used to rate beach tourism activities	-	12.5x12.5km	Historical (1995), RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (2030,2050,2070)
CIT_fair_days	Number of days per month where the index value falls within the range assigned "fair" (Climate Index for Tourism [CIT=4]).	days	12.5x12.5km	Historical (1995), RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (2030,2050,2070)
CIT_good_days	Number of days per month where the index value falls within the range assigned "good" (Climate Index for Tourism [CIT>4]).	days	12.5x12.5km	Historical (1995), RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (2030,2050,2070)

CIT_unfavorable_days	Number of days per month where the index value falls within the range assigned "unfavourable" (Climate Index for Tourism [CIT<4]).	days	12.5x12.5km	Historical (1995), RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (2030,2050,2070)
HCI_daily_index	formulated to evaluate conditions for typical urban tourism activities	-	12.5x12.5km	Historical (1995), RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (2030,2050,2070)
HCI_fair_days	Number of days per month where the index value falls within the range assigned "fair" (Holiday Climate Index [50< HCI <70]).	days	12.5x12.5km	Historical (1995), RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (2030,2050,2070)
HCI_good_days	Number of days per month where the index value falls within the range assigned "good" (Holiday Climate Index [HCI>70]).	days	12.5x12.5km	Historical (1995), RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (2030,2050,2070)
HCI_unfavorable_days	Number of days per month where the index value falls within the range assigned "unfavourable" (Holiday Climate Index [HCI<50]).	days	12.5x12.5km	Historical (1995), RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (2030,2050,2070)

Appendix D – Modelling approaches

Agent Based Macro Models

In ABMs each actor is simulated individually. In the application to economics, actors are individual humans, households, or firms. These types of models are most often applied to small contained systems such as a single neighbourhood. In the case of agent based macro models, this approach is applied to macro economic systems, such as an entire country. ABMs are suited to modelling indirect effects as they are disaggregated, allowing representation of the behaviour of individual actors in response to the hazard event itself or to an induced supply shortage. These responses can be heterogeneous, reflecting differing abilities of actors to respond to events and expectations formed about future events.

The model to be used in the Danube pilot is based on an ABM of the Austrian economy (Poledna et al., 2023) and its customised version for assessment of economic consequences of flood damages (Bachner et al., 2023). The model resolves all actors (households and firms) in the economy for which observations are available in national accounting databases. This allows for the determination of short- to medium-term macroeconomic and sector-level or industry-specific effects of shocks or policies.

The model is intended to overcome the drawbacks of other ABMs, i.e. too many degrees of freedom allowing overmatching of data and lacking forecasting power of macro data (while ABMs have been used to replicate stylised behaviours found in macro data (boom-bust cycles, etc.) they by and large can not predict them).

The model is based around four key approaches: “(1) building an ABM around publicly available macro and microdata of a small open economy, (2) disciplining the individual behaviour of agents (consumers, firms, and banks) through simple heuristics that are calibrated using microdata, (3) using a simple adaptive learning model of expectations through the learning of optimal autoregressive (AR) forecasting rules consistent with macro data, and (4) adopting an empirical validation strategy based on out-of-sample forecasting of macro variables. Furthermore, our detailed ABM contains all sectors of an open economy and can therefore be used for policy analysis.” (Poledna et al., 2023)

The model is solved numerically starting from a chosen year and quarter of observation, to which all model state and flow variables are calibrated. The model is then solved recursively quarter by quarter, up to five years ahead.

The MYRIAD-EU project is structured around five pilot regions: Canary Islands, Veneto, Danube, North Sea, and Scandinavia. Each pilot region is investigated by a different group of researchers using differing methods to investigate the effects of multiple hazards and risks. Existing models within the MYRIAD-EU project are a macro economic agent-based model (Poledna et al., 2023), an integrated assessment meta-model used to investigate dynamic adaptive policy pathways (Haasnoot, 2013), the computable general equilibrium model GRACE (Aaheim et al., 2018), and empirical and machine learning methods. Indirect effects will be described qualitatively in the Canary Islands pilot. Furthermore, the Multiregional Impact Assessment model MRIA (Koks & Thissen, 2016) will be applied to investigate the indirect effects on a Europe wide scale.

Computational General Equilibrium Models

Computational General Equilibrium (CGE) models are numerical economic optimisation models that describe the change in production in an economy based on the balancing of supply and demand in different economic sectors and economic regions or countries. These models follow economic theory assuming consumers maximise utility, firms maximise profits, incomes and expenditures of all economic agents are balanced as are production and consumption of goods and services. With regard to the indirect effects this implies that the modelled economy will adjust immediately to changed demand due to the hazard event, as the economic underpinnings of the

model prescribe frictionless markets. This may cause CGE models to underestimate the duration of the effects of an impact (Koks et al., 2016). In the model context, firms are able to instantaneously ramp up production in response to increased demand, while in reality they are limited by existing production capacity. Increasing production may involve building of new factories, procuring production equipment and hiring workers. All these activities take time to accomplish in the real world, but are abstracted away in the model, allowing for an instantaneous response.

In MYRIAD-EU the CGE model GRACE is used, operated by the members of the Scandinavian pilot. This is a CGE model conceptually capable of representing trade and production of an arbitrary amount of regions. The GRACE model is calibrated based on annual observations in the GTAP database (Aguiar et al., 2022). The limiting factor is the availability of input output data to specify the model relationships. Similarly, the model can be run with different numbers of sectors included. The baseline version of the model (Aaheim et al., 2018) includes separate production of consumption goods, primary energy, goods and services other than agriculture and primary energy, electricity, non-fossil electricity production, and fossil electricity production for each region. The model further includes regional capital stocks and investments as well as regional households driving demand and investment. Investment across regions is possible, balancing the regional returns. Furthermore, the GRACE model is constructed in a set of nonlinear inequalities to reach zero profit, market clearing and income balance conditions. The solution from the GRACE model includes various activity levels, price indexes and income.

Multiregional Impact Assessment Model (MRIA)

The multiregional impact assessment model (Koks & Thissen, 2016) is a recursive dynamic multiregional supply-use model based on input output modelling combined with linear optimisation methods. The model covers the European region at a NUTS 2 level built on the EUREGIO database (Thissen et al., 2018). Production technologies relating inputs to outputs are specific to the individual regions. Damaging production capacity or productivity in a region causes production shifts to other regions or to less efficient production within regions. These shifts in production to unaffected regions are a result of the linear optimisation of production and enable regions not affected by a hazard to benefit from the increased demand during the reconstruction phase. Consequently, this model is very suited to the assessment of interregional and intersectoral indirect effects. The temporal aspect of impacts, the time it takes for damages to be repaired, is an external input of the model.

Appendix E – Tourism resilience scorecard

Table 13: Overall evaluation questions and performance criteria of the Destination Resilience Scorecard.

CSF	Indicator Name	Overall Evaluation Question	Performance Criteria
CSF1: Understanding Risks to Tourism	Perceived Risks to Tourism	How aware are stakeholders of volcanic eruption impacts on tourism?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognition of impact on demand. 2. Awareness of disruptions to travel and safety 3. Concerns about economic impact.
	Impacts on Tourism	How well do stakeholders understand volcanic impacts on tourism?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understanding of impact on tourist arrivals. 2. Awareness of effects on accommodations. 3. Knowledge of service availability disruptions.
	Physical and Financial Risks	Are tourism businesses prepared for physical and financial volcanic risks?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of risk information. 2. Effectiveness of risk assessment models. 3. Adaptability to new volcanic information.
	Tourism Integration in Disaster Plans	How integrated are tourism concerns in disaster planning?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inclusion in national disaster assessments. 2. Economic impact considerations.
CSF2: Planning and Prioritization	Budget and Regulations	Are budgets and regulations aligned to enhance volcanic resilience?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Allocations for warning systems. 2. Support for infrastructural reinforcements. 3. Investment informed by risk assessments.
	Risk Integration in Policy	How are volcanic risks integrated into tourism policy and planning?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Consideration of multi-hazard risks. 2. Inclusion of volcanic scenarios in policy.
	Business Continuity Planning	How effective are business continuity plans for volcanic scenarios?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coverage of volcanic scenarios. 2. Tailoring to tourism sector needs.
	Resilience Commitment	How committed are policymakers to volcanic risk management?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Integration into competitiveness agendas. 2. Stakeholder collaboration.
CSF3: Preparedness and Mitigation	Collaboration on Resilience	How collaborative are resilience strategies for volcanic risks?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stakeholder collaboration 2. Shared responsibility 3. Resource sharing.
	Early Warning Systems	How effective are tourism-tailored early warning systems?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Visibility of systems 2. Catering to tourist safety needs.
	Resilient Infrastructure	How promoted is resilient infrastructure against volcanic activities?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Investments in nature-based solutions. 2. Promotion of disaster-resilient infrastructure.
	Training and Awareness	How comprehensive are training and awareness initiatives?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coverage of volcanic eruption management. 2. Stakeholder training comprehensiveness.

CSF4: Response and Recovery	Crisis Communication	How effective is crisis communication during volcanic events?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coordination among institutions. 2. Use of social media. 3. Public trust maintenance.
	Response and Recovery	How effective are emergency responses to volcanic crises?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Timeliness of evacuations. 2. Effectiveness of emergency services.
	Resilience Initiatives	How effective are resilience initiatives for tourism assets?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Protection of tourism assets. 2. Effectiveness of initiatives.
CSF5: Long Term Resilience Actions	Investment and Diversification	Are long-term resilience investments being made in tourism?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Diversification of tourism products. 2. Infrastructure upgrades. 3. Community capacity building. 4. Strategic investments against hazards. 5. Reduction in dependency on traditional models.
	Long-term Resilience Enhancement	How effective are the long-term resilience policies and initiatives in La Palma?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implementation of targeted training programs. 2. Provision of financial support mechanisms for SMEs. 3. Effectiveness of disaster preparedness programs.
	Resilience Standards and Funds	Are resilience standards effectively supported by funding in La Palma's tourism sector?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compliance with specific resilience and safety standards. 2. Support for businesses meeting sustainability standards. 3. Effective allocation of funds for resilience initiatives.
	Climate Impact Reduction	What measures are in place in La Palma to mitigate the climate impact of tourism and address long-term climate change?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adoption of measures to reduce tourism's climate impact. 2. Efforts to address long-term climate change impacts on tourism. 3. Integration of climate mitigation actions with broader resilience strategies.